

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN

MASTER THESIS

**Development and Implementation of a
Novel Element Tracing Method for a
Reaction Path Analysis and its Application
on a NO_x Path Analysis for Deflagration and
Detonation Processes**

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Zusammenfassung

Development and Implementation of a Novel Element Tracing Method for a Reaction Path Analysis and its Application on a NO_x Path Analysis for Deflagration and Detonation Processes

von Oliver COULMANN

Grenzwerte für Schadstoffemissionen werden immer weiter gesenkt und eine höhere thermische Effizienz technischer Verbrennungssysteme angestrebt. Dadurch gewinnt das Wissen über die zugrundeliegenden kinetischen Entstehungsmechanismen der Schadstoffe immer weiter an Bedeutung. Neu entwickelte Verbrennungskonzepte, wie z. B. pulsed detonation combustion (PDC), und die Realisierbarkeit derartiger Konzepte als praktikable technische Systeme erhöhen den Bedarf an einer zuverlässigen Vorhersagbarkeit der Schadstoffbildung zudem. Diese Arbeit untersucht die Schadstoffbildung bei Verbrennungsprozessen. Speziell werden die zugrundeliegenden kinetischen Mechanismen für die Bildung von Stickstoffmonoxid (NO) in diesen Prozessen erforscht. Im Laufe der Zeit, als mehr NO-Bildungsmechanismen identifiziert und experimentelle Messungen oder Schätzungen der Reaktionsraten verbessert wurden, wurden auch die chemisch-kinetischen Reaktionsmechanismen zunehmend detaillierter. Durch die zunehmende Größe und Komplexität dieser chemisch-kinetischen Reaktionsmechanismen, ist die Differenzierung zwischen Beiträgen zur kompletten NO-Bildung und verschiedenen Submechanismen stetig komplizierter geworden. Die Unterscheidung von Beiträgen von vielfältigen Submechanismen wird zudem durch die Tatsache erschwert, dass viele für die NO-Formation kritische Reaktionen nicht ausschließlich auf einen Submechanismus, sondern viele gleichzeitig zurückzuführen sind.

Es wurde ein Algorithmus entwickelt, der ein neuartiges Verfahren zur Bestimmung der vollständigen Formation einer benutzerdefinierten Zielspezies sowie Beiträge individueller Submechanismen der Formation implementiert und erweitert. In dieser Arbeit wurde der Algorithmus zur Vorhersage der NO-Bildung genutzt. Durch die Verfolgung des Stickstoffflusses von Initiierungsreaktionen, über alle stickstoffhaltigen Zwischenspezies und schließlich zur Oxidation zu NO, kann der Nettofluss zu und von NO bestimmt sowie entsprechend auf einzelne Submechanismen verteilt werden. Der entwickelte Algorithmus verfolgt den Fluss über alle Zwischenspezies an jeder Flammenposition hinweg und resultiert in einer Reaktionspfadanalyse des simulierten Verbrennungsprozesses. Der Algorithmus wurde mithilfe von Ergebnissen aus der Literatur über eine Reihe von Deflagrationsflammen validiert, einschließlich sich frei ausbreitender, stöchiometrischer Methan- und Propanflammen sowie brennerstabilisierten Flammen unterschiedlicher Äquivalenzverhältnisse. Die Ergebnisse bewiesen eine verbesserte Vorhersage der vollständigen NO-Bildung und Bestimmung der Beiträge von Submechanismen im Vergleich zu den Ergebnissen der Literatur. Die Anwendbarkeit des Algorithmus zur Analyse der Detonationsprozesse wurde ebenso untersucht und bestätigt. Auch eine Reaktionspfadanalyse einer stöchiometrischen Methandetonationswelle wurde durchgeführt. Der entwickelte Algorithmus stellt ein hilfreiches Werkzeug zur Untersuchung von Schadstoffbildung in einem breiten Spektrum an Verbrennungsprozessen dar.

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*Abstract***Development and Implementation of a Novel Element Tracing Method for a Reaction Path Analysis and its Application on a NO_x Path Analysis for Deflagration and Detonation Processes**

by Oliver COULMANN

As pollutant emissions limits are reduced, and a greater thermal efficiency of technical combustion systems is desired, knowledge of the underlying kinetic formation mechanisms of pollutants will continue to gain in importance. The development of new combustion concepts, such as pulsed detonation combustion (PDC), and the viability of such concepts as feasible technical systems further increases the need for reliable pollutant formation prediction. This work examines pollutant formation within combustion processes. In particular, the underlying kinetic mechanisms for the formation of nitrogen monoxide (NO) in such processes are investigated. Over time, as more NO formation mechanisms have been identified, and experimental measurements and estimates of reaction rates have improved, chemical kinetic reaction mechanisms have become increasingly detailed. Due to the increased size and complexity of these chemical kinetic reaction mechanisms, differentiating between contributions to total NO formation from various sub-mechanisms has become increasingly difficult. The differentiation of contributions from various sub-mechanisms is further complicated by the fact that many reactions critical to NO formation do not belong exclusively to one sub-mechanism, but are instead shared between many.

An algorithm was developed which implements and expands on a novel element tracing method for determining the total formation of a user defined target species, as well as the contributions from individual formation sub-mechanisms. In this work, the algorithm was used to predict NO formation. By tracing the flux of nitrogen from initiation reactions, through all nitrogen containing intermediate species and subsequently to the oxidation to NO, the net flux to and from NO can be determined and distributed among the individual sub-mechanisms accordingly. The developed algorithm traces the flux through all intermediate species at each flame position, resulting in a reaction path analysis of the simulated combustion process. The algorithm was validated using results from the literature for a range of deflagration flames, including freely propagating, stoichiometric methane and propane flames, and burner stabilised flat flames at different equivalence ratios. The results demonstrated an improved performance for capturing total NO formation and the determination of sub-mechanism contributions compared to results from the literature. The applicability of the algorithm for the analysis of detonation processes was also examined and confirmed, and a reaction path analysis of a stoichiometric methane detonation wave conducted. The developed algorithm presents a useful tool for the investigation of pollutant formation in a wide range of combustion processes.

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List of Abbreviations

CalTech	California (Institute of) Technology
EIA	U.S Energy Information Administration
IEO	International Energy Outlook
JSR	Jet Stirred Reactor
LLNL	Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory
PDC	Pulsed Detonation Combustion
PDE	Pulsed Detonation Engine
PFR	Plug Flow Reactor
POLIMI	POLItecnico (di) MILano
PSR	Perfectly Stirred Reactor
UCSD	University (of) California (at) San Diego
ZND	Zel'dovich (von) Neumann Döring

List of Symbols

c_p	specific heat capacity of gas	$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
c_{p_i}	specific heat capacity of i th species	$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
c_0	speed of sound in upstream state	m s^{-1}
$dev_{\text{NO-ROP}}$	deviation in total predicted NO formation between the algorithm and Cantera	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
dev_{sub}	deviation in predicted sub-mechanism contribution to NO formation between the algorithm and Bohon et al.	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
$f_{c_{sp,sub}}$	flux correction factor for species sp and sub-mechanism sub	-
$f_{i,sub}$	inflow flux from species i and sub-mechanism sub	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
$f_{i,j,sp,sub}$	flux between species sp and j from initiation reactions in sub-mechanism sub	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
F_{sp}	total global inflow flux to species sp	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
$F_{sp,i}$	global inflow flux to species sp from species i	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
FT_{sub}	sub-mechanism sub contribution to target species rate of production	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
$g_{j,sub}$	outflow flux to species j and sub-mechanism sub	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
G_{sp}	total global outflow flux from species sp	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
$G_{sp,j}$	global outflow flux from species sp to species j	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
$GF_{i,j}$	global flux from species j to species i	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
h	specific enthalpy of gas	J kg^{-1}
h_0	specific enthalpy of gas in upstream state	J kg^{-1}
h_1	specific enthalpy of gas in downstream state	J kg^{-1}
h_i	specific enthalpy of the i th species	J kg^{-1}
h_f^0	specific enthalpy of formation	J kg^{-1}
$h_{f_i}^0$	specific enthalpy of formation of the i th species	J kg^{-1}
k	reaction rate coefficient	*
k_f	forward reaction rate coefficient	*
k_r	reverse reaction rate coefficient	*
\dot{m}	mass flux of gas	kg s^{-1}
$mf_{i,j,sub}$	molar flux from species j to species i for sub-mechanism sub	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
mf_{res}	residual of molar fluxes	-
M	Mach number	-
M_0	Mach number in upstream state	-
M_{CJ}	Mach number in CJ state	-
MF_{sp}	molar flux to species sp from all sub-mechanisms	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
$MF_{sp,sub}$	molar flux to species sp from sub-mechanism sub	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
n	molar density of gas mixture	mol m^{-3}
n_i	molar density of the i th species	mol m^{-3}
nc_i	non-dimensional coefficient of the i th species	-

p	gas pressure	Pa
p_0	pressure of gas in upstream state	Pa
p_1	pressure of gas in downstream state	Pa
p_{CJ}	pressure of gas in Chapman Jouguet state	Pa
p_{vN}	pressure of gas in von Neumann state	Pa
p_i	partial pressure of the i th species	Pa
P_{sp}^i	pool term for species sp at flame position i	mol m^{-3}
$P_{sp,sub}$	pool term for species sp and sub-mechanism sub at current flame position	mol m^{-3}
$P_{sp,sub}^i$	pool term for species sp and sub-mechanism sub at flame position i	mol m^{-3}
\hat{p}	ratio of downstream to upstream gas pressure	-
q	heat release	J kg^{-1}
q'	dimensionless heat release	-
R	specific gas constant of air	$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
Rf	reaction flux	mol s^{-1}
RPA_{res}	reaction path analysis residual	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
S_{sp}	total global source term for species sp	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
$S_{sp,sub}$	source term for species sp and sub-mechanism sub	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
S_L	laminar flame speed	m s^{-1}
S_{L_i}	laminar flame speed at flame position i	m s^{-1}
T	gas temperature	K
T_0	temperature of gas in upstream state	K
T_1	temperature of gas in downstream state	K
T_{CJ}	temperature of gas in Chapman Jouguet state	K
T_{vN}	temperature of gas in von Neumann state	K
u_0	velocity of gas in upstream state	m s^{-1}
u_1	velocity of gas in downstream state	m s^{-1}
v_0	specific volume of gas in upstream state	$\text{m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1}$
v_1	specific volume of gas in downstream state	$\text{m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1}$
\hat{v}	ratio of downstream to upstream gas specific volume	-
\vec{v}	fluid velocity	m s^{-1}
\vec{v}_i	mean molecular velocity of the i th species	m s^{-1}
W_i	molecular weight of the i th species	g mol^{-1}
X_i	mole fraction of the i th species	-
Y_i	mass fraction of the i th species	-
$\eta_{sp,sub}$	allocation factor for species sp and sub-mechanism sub	-
κ	ratio of specific heats of gas	-
κ_0	ratio of specific heats of gas in upstream state	-
κ_1	ratio of specific heats of gas in downstream state	-
$\gamma_{sp,sub}$	flux case I allocation factor for species sp and sub-mechanism sub	-
ν_S	stoichiometric coefficient of species S	-
ψ_i	reaction rate	mol s^{-1}
ρ	mass density of gas mixture	kg m^{-3}
ρ_0	mass density of gas in upstream state	kg m^{-3}
ρ_1	mass density of gas in downstream state	kg m^{-3}
ρ_{CJ}	mass density of gas in Chapman Jouguet state	kg m^{-3}
ρ_{vN}	mass density of gas in von Neumann state	kg m^{-3}
ρ_i	partial mass density of the i th species	kg m^{-3}

$\sigma_{sp,sub}$	flux case II, III allocation factor for species sp and sub-mechanism sub	-
ω_r	reaction rate of reaction r	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$

* units dependent on reaction order

Dedicated to my parents.

Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter provides an introduction to the topic of the thesis. The motivation for the research conducted is explained, followed by a detailed review of existing work and literature. Background information into reaction path analyses, NO_x formation mechanisms, and pulsed detonation combustion is provided.

1.1 Motivation

Over the past decades, emissions produced by combustion have presented an ever increasing major technical problem and challenge for the future. One method to limit greenhouse gas emissions is through the continued increase in efficiency of combustion processes utilised in power generation. The constant increase in conventional gas turbine efficiency has made further significant increases in efficiency difficult, and subsequently led to the development of new combustion concepts, such as pulsed detonation combustion (PDC) [21]. Concepts such as PDC promise a significant increase in thermal efficiency. Regulation has also led to the introduction and subsequent reduction of pollutant emissions limits over time. For both conventional combustion systems, as well as new concepts such as PDC, the study of underlying pollutant formation mechanisms will continue to grow in importance. Particularly the formation of pollutants such as NO_x in new combustion concepts will require increased attention as the concepts continue to be developed.

Figure 1.1 below shows the worldwide energy consumption as reported in the International Energy Outlook (IEO) 2018 and published by the U.S Energy Information Administration (EIA) [2]. The plot shows the energy consumption based on the energy source (i.e. natural gas, coal etc.) up to the year 2018, as well as the predicted energy consumption for each energy source for the years 2018 - 2040.

Several important observations can be made referring to the the data presented in Figure 1.1. Firstly, the constant increasing trend in worldwide energy consumption to the present day can be clearly identified across all energy sources. There are only a few exceptions where energy consumption has decreased, most notably around the year 2008 in which a decrease in energy consumption for petroleum, coal, and natural gas energy sources can be seen. The energy consumption for coal also exhibits one or two other small decreases between the years 1990 - 2018. Another interesting observation is the high rate of increase of energy consumption from renewables in the mid 2000's. Despite the aforementioned minor exceptions, the continual increasing trend in energy consumption across all energy sources on a macro level is clear.

FIGURE 1.1: Worldwide energy consumption per energy source. Data obtained from the International Energy Outlook (IEO) 2018 [2]. To the right of the dashed grey line are the predicted trends for energy consumption up to 2040.

The data presented by the EIA in Figure 1.1 also clearly shows the predicted continued increase in energy consumption across almost all energy sources in the future (years 2018 - 2040). The forecast provided in the IEO 2018 highlights a few key points. While energy consumption from coal and nuclear sources are expected to plateau and potentially even decrease slightly, the energy consumption from petroleum, natural gas, and renewable energy sources is expected to continue to increase dramatically in line with the expected global increase in energy consumption.

Even as the share of power generated by renewable energy sources has, and continues to, grow over time, the continued use of fossil fuels for electricity generation during a transition to complete carbon neutral electricity generation remains highly likely, or even necessary. As many renewable energy sources, for example wind and solar energy, fluctuate greatly, the need for consistent, reliable power production will only increase as more emphasis is placed on electricity generation by renewable energy sources [21]. Combined with a potential phasing out of particularly high carbon dioxide emitting processes, such as electricity generation by coal power plants as forecast by EIA [2], the combustion of natural gas in gas turbines presents an opportunity for meeting the electricity generation required, while also providing the flexibility needed to operate effectively in conjunction with electricity production from renewable energy sources [21]. The continued use of conventional combustion systems, as well as the development of innovative concepts, necessitates a continued research effort into the formation of pollutant emissions. Only with knowledge of the underlying formation mechanisms of such pollutants or emissions can engineering solutions for the reduction of such emissions be developed.

NO_x is the generic term used to describe the combined nitric oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) emissions, which both contribute to air pollution. NO is not considered to

be hazardous at typical ambient conditions but contributes to the formation of acid rain, and reacts with stratospheric ozone to form NO_2 . NO_2 can irritate airways in the respiratory system and aggravate respiratory diseases. It also interacts with chemicals in the atmosphere to form acid rain [3]. Recently, NO_x emissions have received increased attention, particularly in the transportation sector. Due to the reduction of allowable emissions limits, the calculation and modelling of NO_x emissions during combustion processes has gained in importance. The modelling of NO_x emissions in the aforementioned novel combustion processes, such as PDC, therefore presents an interesting and necessary area of research to be conducted, should such concepts become viable and able to be technically implemented in the future. This work focuses on the development of an algorithm for conducting reaction path analyses in combustion processes. One potential application of the algorithm is the prediction of NO_x emissions of the proposed PDC combustion process. Ultimately the algorithm is intended to be utilised as a post-processing tool for research into the underlying kinetic formation mechanisms of pollutants and other compounds of interest. Only with an increased understanding of formation mechanisms, is the development of technical engineering solutions for reducing pollutants possible. One such example is the lean operation of industrial gas turbines, which reduces NO_x emissions by limiting their formation via the Zel'dovich mechanism and could only be developed as a result of an understanding of the underlying formation mechanism.

1.2 Literature Review

1.2.1 Chemical Kinetic Reaction Mechanisms

A detailed literature review was undertaken to identify existing reaction mechanisms including nitrogen chemistry. Many of the developed reaction mechanisms are based on several decades of research work and collaboration between different research groups. The reaction mechanisms are continuously updated and refined. All kinetic mechanisms depend on validation with experimental results. The pool of available kinetic mechanisms is therefore always expanding, as new experimental data for previously untested conditions becomes available. One such example is the development of mechanisms for higher pressures in recent years [82].

In what has become a widely cited study, Miller & Bowman developed a reaction mechanism for the combustion of hydrocarbons with nitrogen chemistry [75]. The nitrogen subset of the reaction mechanism includes the formation of NO_x via the thermal, prompt, fuel, thermal De- NO_x , RAPRENO $_x$, and N_2O mechanisms. The full mechanism consists of 234 reactions. The nitrogen subset of the reaction mechanism was used and expanded upon in many other studies since being published.

Goswami et al. from Eindhoven University of Technology undertook their own extensive literature review of existing mechanisms and developed a new reaction mechanism for calculating H_2/O_2 combustion and NO_x prediction [40]. The mechanism was developed to simulate combustion of lean premixed mixtures, $\phi < 0.8$, at elevated pressures of up to 20 atm. The results were compared to calculations using reaction mechanisms developed by Rasmussen et al. [82], Frassoldati et al. [27], and the GRI-Mech 3.0 mechanism [89]. The mechanism developed by Goswami et al. uses data from many other published papers and consists of 237 reactions. The nitrogen chemistry subset of the developed reaction mechanism is reproduced from the work of Volkov et al. [95].

The nitrogen chemistry reaction mechanism developed by Volkov et al. [95] consists of 29 reactions and 11 species. The mechanism is an update of the mechanism developed by Konnov et al. consisting of 27 reactions and 11 species [53]. The mechanism fails to accurately predict the N_2O burning velocities. For the purposes of this study the mechanism was still deemed to be of use, as the experimental data on NO_x decomposition considered in the research by Volkov et al. was satisfactorily reproduced using the developed mechanism.

Rasmussen et al. conducted lean $\text{CO}/\text{H}_2/\text{O}_2/\text{NO}_x$ oxidation experiments and developed a new kinetic mechanism describing H_2/O_2 , CO/CO_2 , and NO_x chemistry [83]. The experiments were conducted for temperatures at 600-900 K and pressures of 20-100 bar. The HNO , HONO/HNO_2 and HONO_2 subsets of the reaction mechanism were developed using existing mechanisms developed by Allen et al. [4], Skreiberg et al. [88], and Park et al. [78]. The developed mechanism consists of 67 reactions, of which 38 belong to the NO_x subset.

Rasmussen et al. also developed a detailed kinetic reaction mechanism for the oxidation of methane and ethane [82]. The developed mechanism was validated using experimental results in the intermediate temperature range of approximately 500-1100 K and pressures up to 100 bar. The mechanism was also extended to include important reactions at high temperatures, which were validated using experimental shock tube, laminar flame, and flow reactor results. The developed mechanism consists of 229 reactions. Supplementing the developed reaction mechanism with the NO_x subset developed by the same group for $\text{CO}/\text{H}_2/\text{O}_2/\text{NO}_x$ oxidation provides a potential light hydrocarbon reaction mechanism consisting of 267 reactions.

Allen et al. conducted flow reactor experiments using $\text{CO}/\text{N}_2\text{O}/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{N}_2$ mixtures at 950-1123 K and a pressure range of 3-15 atm [4]. The experimental results were used to develop a detailed kinetic mechanism. The results showed the effect of hydrogenous impurities on the kinetic reaction rate constants. The developed reaction mechanism was used by Rasmussen et al. and expanded on to develop a new kinetic reaction mechanism as described above [82].

Skreiberg et al. developed a kinetic mechanism for the oxidation of NH_3 under fuel rich conditions and moderate temperatures [88]. The mechanism was validated based on experimental results by Hasegawa et al. [42] and is recommended for modelling the reduction of NO in biomass combustion or NO formation in gas combustion. The developed kinetic mechanism includes C1 and C2 chemistry adopted from Glarborg et al. [35] and nitrogen chemistry based mainly on previous work by Miller et al. [73, 75, 76], and Glarborg et al. [38].

Glarborg et al. developed a kinetic reaction mechanism for thermal DeNO_x [38]. The mechanism was validated using experimental flow reactor results and showed reasonable agreement. The formation of N_2O was also modelled and showed good agreement with experimental results. The developed reaction mechanism is based largely on the mechanism developed by Miller and Bowman [75] with changes made to certain reaction constants and parameters. The computational procedure also included modelling of surface effects which proved to be unimportant for experiments carried out in low surface to volume quartz reactors.

Miller et al. investigated ammonia flames and proposed a reaction mechanism for the oxidation of ammonia [73]. The proposed mechanism was validated by experimental results which showed good agreement except for in very rich flames. The mechanism is therefore best suited for the modelling of ammonia oxidation with nitrogen chemistry

under lean conditions. The mechanism is largely derived from previous work by the same research group. The research concluded that under lean conditions, NO is formed through the HNO intermediate [38]. The extended Zel'dovich mechanism dominates NO formation under rich conditions.

Miller et al. presented an updated kinetic reaction mechanism for the thermal DeNO_x pathway [76]. The developed mechanism expanded on the mechanism by the same research group developed by Glarborg et al. [38]. The reaction rate constants for two reactions were updated. The results showed good agreement with experimental results from the literature over a wide range of temperatures.

Park et al. studied the kinetics of and developed a mechanism for the thermal reduction of NO₂ by H₂ in a temperature range of 602-954 K and for a number of different mixtures [78]. Experiments were carried out and a kinetic reaction mechanism developed for the H₂ + NO₂ system.

Frassoldati et al. from the Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI) developed and validated a kinetic reaction mechanism for the modelling of NO_x and simple hydrocarbons during thermal oxidation and reburning at high temperatures [27]. The work expanded on previous research by the same research group which modelled NO and hydrocarbon interactions at low temperatures [24]. The base hydrocarbon oxidation mechanism was previously developed by Ranzi et al. [81]. The model developed by Frassoldati et al. was validated using experimental results from several different research groups. The reaction mechanism consists of 2141 reactions and 115 species.

Marinov et al., from the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL), developed a detailed kinetic model to investigate the role of hydrocarbon oxidation in NO-NO₂ conversion [62]. The hydrocarbons included in the mechanism are methane, ethane, propane, ethene, propene, and acetylene. The reaction mechanism developed consists of 638 reactions and 126 species. The base mechanism for the hydrocarbon oxidation was taken from the mechanisms previously developed by the same research group [14, 59, 60, 61]. The nitrogen chemistry was added to the mechanism based on the chemistry taken from GRI-Mech 2.11 [11] and Atkinson [6].

The GRI-Mech 3.0 reaction mechanism was developed by a research group at UC Berkeley and is the successor to the GRI-Mech 2.11 mechanism [11]. GRI-Mech 3.0 consists of 325 reactions and 53 species detailing the combustion of natural gas, including nitrogen chemistry [89].

Zhang et al. developed a detailed chemical kinetic reaction mechanism for hydrogen and syngas combustion [100]. The developed NO_x subset of the reaction mechanism consists of 66 reactions and was validated with experimental data. A flux analysis was also performed to provide an overview of the NO formation pathways.

Watanabe et al. carried out a study to investigate NO_x formation in staged combustion [96]. Experimental measurements of a flat methane flame were made to determine NO_x formation. OH was also measured using chemiluminescence. The results were compared to numerical simulations investigating NO_x formation and reduction mechanisms. The numerical work was completed using CHEMKIN-PRO and the GRI-Mech 3.0 reaction mechanism [89]. It was concluded that the NO_x emissions could be significantly reduced by staged combustion.

Lee et al. carried out a numerical study investigating the effect of CO₂ addition on flame structure and NO_x formation [56]. A CH₄ counterflow diffusion flame was simulated for the study. The GRI 2.11 kinetic reaction mechanism consisting of 49 species and 279

reactions was implemented [11]. Changes in NO_x formation were mainly attributed to the thermal effect of CO₂ addition.

Glarborg et al. developed a kinetic reaction mechanism for the oxidation of C1 and C2 hydrocarbons, including nitrogen chemistry [35]. The mechanism was based on several other numerical and experimental studies. The hydrocarbon oxidation subset was based on previous work by Miller et al. [34, 72, 75]. The nitrogen chemistry subset of the reaction mechanism expands on the reaction mechanism presented by Miller & Bowman [75]. Implementing the information and findings provided by other published research into the specific reaction parameters [31, 33, 36, 38, 39, 74], the mechanism was updated and showed reasonably good agreement with experimental results [35]. The reaction mechanism consists of 438 reactions.

More recently, Glarborg et al. undertook an extensive review of existing reaction mechanisms and modelling of nitrogen chemistry [37]. Mechanism subsets representing the various NO_x formation pathways were presented and validated with experimental results. The base hydrocarbon oxidation mechanism was based on work carried out by the same research group into the high-pressure oxidation of methane and ethane [29, 43, 44]. The development of the base mechanism for the oxidation of methane conducted by Hashemi et al. again drew on multiple other sources and previously developed mechanisms [44]. The H₂ subset was taken from the work by the same research group [45]. The CO/H₂ oxidation subset developed by Rasmussen et al. was used [83]. The base mechanism for hydrocarbon oxidation was developed using the mechanisms developed by Rasmussen et al. [82] and Gimenez-Lopez et al. [29, 30]. The development of the methanol subset of the mechanism was based on the work conducted by Aranda et al. [5] and Rasmussen et al. [84]. The ethane subset of the reaction mechanism was developed using the work of Hashemi et al. [43], where the previously developed mechanisms for H₂ [45], CH₄ [44], and C₂H₂ [29] were referenced and expanded on. The thermodynamic and transport properties were adapted from the work by Rasmussen et al. [82]. The development of the reaction mechanism for the oxidation of ethane [43] was again based on previous studies and existing reaction mechanisms. The mechanisms developed by Rasmussen et al. [82], Hashemi et al. [44], and Gimenez-Lopez et al. [29] were expanded and improved on.

The interactions between hydrocarbons and nitrogen were also adapted from other studies [35, 65, 66]. The nitrogen chemistry consists of multiple subsets, each of which describe the formation of NO_x through a different reaction pathway. The developed kinetic reaction mechanism includes the thermal/Zel'dovich, prompt, N₂O and NNH, oxidation of HCN, oxidation of HCNO, and oxidation of NH₃ reaction pathways, which all contribute to the formation of NO.

The thermal subset of nitrogen chemistry was derived from the pioneering work conducted by Yakov Zel'dovich [99]. The Zel'dovich pathway represents the most important source for the high temperature formation of NO. The reaction pathway is well established and consists of three reactions. The reaction rate constants were adapted from other research published. The experimental validation of the reaction rate constants of the thermal subset remains challenging, due to a lack of experimental data. However, the uncertainty of calculations using the thermal subset were expected to be small by the authors [37].

The rate constants for the prompt subset are mostly derived from other published experimental work. The most important reactions within the prompt subset are characterised

using experimental results from unpublished research by the same research group as well as other published papers [7, 20, 23, 90, 101].

The N_2O formation pathway was proposed by Malte et al. [58]. The reaction subset for the formation of NO via N_2O was developed by referencing work conducted by Baulch et al. [7], Klippenstein et al. [51], and Meagher et al. [63].

The reaction subset based on the formation of NNH is largely derived from the work conducted by Klippenstein et al. [51], which reviewed the NNH reaction mechanism and provided updates to the constants based on experimental results and theoretical considerations.

The HCN oxidation subset of the reaction mechanism is based on the work by Dagaut et al. [19]. Improvements to the mechanism subset were made applying the modifications suggested by Glarborg et al. [32]. Rate constants for the HCN oxidation subset were adopted from several other experimental investigations into specific reactions within the subset [7, 12, 25, 28, 32, 72, 74, 75, 91, 97, 102].

The HCNO oxidation subset is adapted from previous work by the same research group [7, 31, 35, 74, 75]. Further modifications to the subset were also made using the data obtained from several experimental studies [46, 47, 48, 67, 68, 69, 79, 93, 97, 98] and theoretical work [71, 86].

The ammonia subset of the reaction mechanism is based mostly on the recent work by Klippenstein et al. [51], which draws on many other sources for determining rate constants for the subset. The reaction mechanism developed by Glarborg et al. [37] also includes subsets for the selective non-catalytic reduction of NO and reburn.

Dagaut et al. developed a kinetic reaction mechanism for the oxidation of C1-C4 hydrocarbons including nitrogen chemistry [18]. The base mechanism was taken from previous work conducted by Tan et al. [92]. The NO_x sub-mechanism was taken from work conducted by the same research group [17]. The mechanism was validated with experimentally obtained flame data and consists of 892 reactions and 113 species.

The Konnov0.6 mechanism developed by Konnov [52] was based on the original 0.5 release developed by the same author [15]. Several improvements were made to the original mechanism which had been developed for the combustion modelling of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, formaldehyde, methanol, and C1-C3 hydrocarbon species. The original mechanism also included H/C/N/O reactions for NO_x formation and reburning. The updated 0.6 release of the mechanism included a review of the thermodynamic data and rate constants based on new research. Modifications were made to the low temperature methane oxidation, NNH route of NO formation, and hydrogen sub-mechanism. NCN and HNCN reactions not present in the 0.5 mechanism were also added to the 0.6 release [55]. The developed mechanism consists of 1231 reactions and 129 species.

El bakali et al. developed the GDF-Kin 3.0 reaction mechanism by updating the existing GDF-Kin 2.0 reaction mechanism [22]. The GDF-Kin 3.0 mechanism was created by combining GDF-Kin 2.0 mechanism with the NO_x sub-mechanism from Dagaut et al. [17]. The mechanism was then further updated to include prompt-NO formation, resulting in the GDF-Kin 3.0_NCN reaction mechanism. The mechanism was validated using experimental results from the same research group [80], as well as data from the literature.

Lamoureux et al. developed and validated the NOMecha2.0 reaction mechanism [55]. The developed mechanism was mainly based on the existing GDF-Kin 3.0_NCN reaction mechanism developed by El bakali et al. [22] which is an updated mechanism based

on the GDF-Kin 2.0 reaction mechanism. The NOMecha2.0 reaction mechanism is the successor to the NOMecha1.1 mechanism developed by the same research group. The NOMecha1.1 mechanism is based on the work of [31, 35, 38]. The NOMecha2.0 mechanism consists of 934 reactions and 123 species and has been validated for the combustion of methane, ethane, propane, and acetylene using experimental data from the literature.

The University of California San Diego (UCSD) has developed a range of chemical kinetic reaction mechanisms for the combustion of various fuels. The mechanisms are intended to focus on conditions relevant to flames, high temperature ignition, and detonation [64]. The complete San Diego mechanism includes reactions and species for the combustion of hydrocarbons up to and including butane. With the addition of the nitrogen chemistry sub-mechanism the San Diego mechanism for the combustion of hydrocarbons with nitrogen chemistry consists of 321 reactions and 70 species.

Table 1.1 below provides an overview of a selection of the chemical kinetic reaction mechanisms identified in the literature review. The selected reaction mechanisms were chosen as they all include nitrogen chemistry, and were developed based on different existing mechanisms and experimental results.

TABLE 1.1: Overview of identified chemical kinetic reaction mechanisms.

Mechanism #	Author	Reference	Notes
1	Glarborg et al.	[37]	Mechanism for the oxidation of hydrocarbons consisting of 1397 reactions and 151 species. NOx sub-mechanism consists of approximately 450 reactions. Validated by very large set of experimental results. Each subset of the NOx sub-mechanism is therefore validated for different conditions, detailed in the reference.
2	POLIMI	[27]	Mechanism for the oxidation of hydrocarbons consisting of 2141 reactions and 115 species. NOx sub-mechanism consists of 263 reactions and 30 species. Mechanism validated in approximate temperature range of 600-1450 K for atmospheric pressure only. Validated using results from plug flow reactor (PFR) and jet-stirred reactor (JSR) experiments.
3	LLNL	[62]	Combustion of C1-C4 hydrocarbons with nitrogen chemistry. Reaction mechanism consists of 638 reactions and 126 species. The NOx sub-mechanism is adapted from GRI-Mech 2.11 and Atkinson [6] and consists of 155 reactions. Validated for atmospheric pressure and a temperature range of 600-1100 K.
4	Konnov 0.6	[52]	Hydrocarbon reaction mechanism with nitrogen chemistry. Consists of 1231 reactions and 129 species. NOx sub-mechanism is very similar to that of the 0.5 release, consisting of 241 reactions and 31 species. Reaction mechanism is validated for pressures up to 20 atmospheres in a temperature range of 1000-1750 K for propane-air mixtures.
5	NOMecha2.0	[55]	NOx sub-mechanism based on GDFKin 3.0_NCN mechanism. NOMecha2.0 consists of 934 reactions and 123 species for the oxidation of light hydrocarbons. NOx sub-mechanism consists of 237 reactions. Validated for low pressures only.
6	San Diego	[49]	Hydrocarbon oxidation with nitrogen chemistry. Mechanism with nitrogen chemistry consists of 321 reactions and 70 species. Validated for co-flow diffusion flames. Validated for ambient conditions and pressures of 40 bar at temperatures up to 855 K.
7	GRI-Mech 3.0	[89]	Mechanism developed by the Gas Research Institute for the combustion of natural gas including nitrogen chemistry. The 3.0 mechanism is the successor to the GRI 2.11 mechanism and consists of 325 reactions and 53 species.
8	Dagaut et al.	[18]	Hydrocarbon reaction mechanism consisting of 892 reactions and 113 species.
9	Rasmussen et al.	[82]	Base mechanism developed for the oxidation of hydrocarbons, consisting of 229 reactions. The NOx subset of smaller CO/H ₂ /O ₂ /NOx mechanism could be added to create a hydrocarbon reaction mechanism consisting of 267 reactions. Mechanism incorporated in the development of the reaction mechanism by Glarborg et al. [37].
10	Zhang et al.	[100]	Hydrogen and syngas reaction mechanism with NOx subset consisting of 66 reactions.
11	Goswami et al.	[40]	Reaction mechanism for H ₂ oxidation including nitrogen chemistry. NOx subset of reaction mechanism is from Volkov et al. [95]. Mechanism consists of 237 reactions.

1.2.2 Reaction Path Analysis

Critical to the usefulness of any numerical simulation or calculation is the interpretation of the results produced. In the field of combustion kinetics, obtaining an understanding of the simulation results is difficult due to the very large, complex reaction mechanisms which are typically implemented. As such, further techniques are often applied to gain a deeper understanding of the modelling and to recognise the implications of the simulation results [41]. One such technique is the reaction path analysis. The analysis produces a reaction path diagram, which gives insight into the exchange of material among species in a chemically reacting system [41]. From this a deeper understanding of the sub-mechanisms and intermediate species which are formed in the system during combustion can be gained. In technical applications, this knowledge can be used to target specific elementary reactions which may be responsible for the formation of undesirable products. One such example is the lean operation of modern gas turbines, which lowers flame temperatures and therefore reduces the formation of NO_x due to the Zel'dovich formation mechanism. Further detail on the various NO_x formation mechanisms is given in Chapter 2.

Reaction path diagrams can be divided into either schematic diagrams, or diagrams which provide quantitative information. Schematic reaction path diagrams depict chemical mechanisms by using arrows to represent theoretically possible reactant-product dependencies. While thicker arrows may be used to highlight an important reaction, the thickness of the arrows in a schematic reaction path diagram does not provide quantitative information on the material exchange among species. Other reaction path diagrams provide quantitative information on the rate of reactant - product dependencies by using variable path weights to provide an indication of the material exchange represented by a specific arrow. Several methods are used to determine path/arrow weights including reaction or chemical flux, and sensitivity analyses [41]. Figure 1.2 shows an example of a quantitative reaction path diagram for the combustion of methane.

The use of reaction or chemical flux for quantifying path weights is called integral reaction path analysis, as the flux is a measure of amount of substance transformed per unit volume per unit time. When the path weight is calculated by considering the production or consumption of species, the integral path analysis can lead to ambiguous results. Using the reaction flux of conserved scalars, an element such as H, N, O etc. can be chosen and the corresponding reaction flux calculated for two species using the following equation:

$$Rf(e, sp_1, sp_2) = \sum_i \int_V nc_i(e, sp_1, sp_2) \psi_i dV \quad (1.1)$$

The magnitude of the reaction flux, Rf , calculated using equation 1.1 determines the width of the path in the reaction diagram and the sign of the calculated value determines the direction of the arrow between sp_1 and sp_2 [41]. The non-dimensional coefficient, nc_i , is determined based on how many elements, e , are transferred from sp_1 to sp_2 in the conventional forward direction of the reaction. The reaction rate is denoted by ψ_i . Care must be taken when computing the nc_i values for elementary reactions using the reaction flux of conserved scalars method, as the chosen element, e , may be found in two reactants and two products [41].

The integral reaction path analysis therefore provides information on how material is exchanged between various identified species of interest. However, no information is

FIGURE 1.2: Example of quantitative reaction path diagram for the combustion of methane. The width of the arrows represents the magnitude of flux between species.

provided on the formation of certain species due to a certain reaction sub-mechanism (e.g. Zel'dovich mechanism). As the various formation sub-mechanisms all contribute to the formation or depletion of a species, distinguishing between the contributions from each sub-mechanism is difficult [10]. A common approach utilised in many studies is to conduct simulations with certain reactions or sets of reactions removed from the NO_x reaction mechanism. The results are then compared to those using an unaltered NO_x reaction mechanism, with the difference in result being attributed to the removed reactions representing a certain sub-mechanism. For example, if the prompt NO_x formation mechanism is to be investigated, a simulation with the complete NO_x reaction mechanism will be performed and compared to a simulation conducted with the prompt subset of the NO_x reaction mechanism removed. The difference in simulation results (i.e. NO_x formation) can then be attributed to the prompt NO_x formation mechanism. However, this approach is problematic, as the removal of certain reactions or subsets of reactions can have other, unintended consequences on the formation of NO_x [10].

Bohon et al. presented a new method for conducting a reaction path analysis to avoid the significant limitation of removing a subset of reactions from the reaction mechanism [10]. The authors proposed a novel element tracing method, in which the tracing element, nitrogen in the case of NO_x formation, which has been unfixed from inert molecular nitrogen N₂ is traced through all other intermediate species containing the tracing element

(HCN, NH etc.) to the target species (i.e. NO). The various sub-mechanisms can then be distinguished from one another. The advantage of the method proposed is that the underlying reaction mechanism remains unaltered, and as such the complete set of nitrogen chemistry is always applied. Furthermore, the simulation of the combustion process does not have to be modified at all, as the reaction path analysis can be performed as a pure post-processing calculation using the obtained simulation results. An example of the result of a reaction path analysis using the novel element tracing method can be seen in Figure 1.3 below.

FIGURE 1.3: Example of the result of a reaction path analysis using the element tracing method proposed by Bohon et al. [10]. The black circles (\circ) represent the total NO formation at the various positions in the flame. The various coloured lines represent the contributions to the NO formation from the different sub-mechanisms, as listed in the plot legend. The dashed black line (- - -) is the sum of the individual sub-mechanism contributions.

The various coloured lines represent the contribution to NO formation from the different sub-mechanisms (e.g. prompt, thermal etc.). The sum of the contributions is shown by the black dashed line (- - -). The total NO formation is also shown by the black circle markers (\circ). It is clear that the element tracing method captures most of the total NO formation and the individual sub-mechanisms reasonably well.

While the results provide a good insight into the various relevant sub-mechanisms for the formation of NO in flames, the element tracing method has limitations. In particular, in the work by Bohon et al. the element tracing method was implemented such that it could only be applied to flame simulations which were conducted using one specific chemical kinetic reaction mechanism. The method also required the definition of a burnout sub-mechanism, which is shown by the cyan line (—) shown in Figure 1.3. The burnout sub-mechanism represents the contribution to NO formation from species which accumulate in the flame. Ideally, the burnout contribution should be incorporated within the other sub-mechanisms, depending on which one of them led to the accumulation of the

species being considered. Furthermore, as can be seen in Figure 1.3, the total NO rate of production, represented by the black dashed line (- - -), does not completely match the true total rate of production, represented by the black circles (o). The aim of this work is to expand upon the element tracing method to address the aforementioned limitations, and develop an algorithm implementing the improved element tracing method which can be utilised to conduct reaction path analyses for various fuel types and combustion processes.

Chapter 2

Theoretical Background

2.1 Detonation

Combustion waves transform reactants into products and propagate away from the ignition source, releasing chemical potential energy stored in chemical bonds, which is converted into thermal and kinetic energy of the combustion products [57]. When considering combustion phenomena, or undertaking modelling or simulations of technical combustion systems, it is important to differentiate between two main types of combustion waves, *deflagration* and *detonation* waves. Deflagration waves are typically observed and described as flames. For example, the flames produced by candles, matches, or bunsen burners are deflagration waves. Deflagration waves propagate at relatively low subsonic velocities and are mainly influenced by diffusion processes. The flame front of a deflagration always propagates in the direction of the unburned gas. The pressure drops across a deflagration wave, as the burned gas expands due to the reactions which occur in the reaction zone.

Conversely, detonation waves propagate at supersonic velocities. A detonation wave is effectively a reacting shock wave, in which a leading shock wave nearly instantaneously increases the pressure and temperature of the gas. A reaction zone is coupled to the leading shock wave, in which the gas reacts, further increasing the post shock temperature and decreasing the pressure. Overall, there is a large increase in pressure across a detonation wave, due to the leading compression shock wave. A comparison of the typical properties before and after a deflagration and detonation wave is provided in the Table 2.1 below. The values listed are either the wave Mach number (M_1), or ratios between properties downstream (subscript 1) and upstream (subscript 0) of the wave, and are therefore dimensionless.

TABLE 2.1: Comparison of characteristic deflagration and detonation properties [54].

	Deflagration	Detonation
M_1	0.0001-0.03	5-10
u_1/u_0	4-6	0.4-0.7
p_1/p_0	0.98	13-55
T_1/T_0	4-16	8-21
ρ_1/ρ_0	0.06-0.25	1.7-2.6

2.1.1 Zel'dovich - von Neumann - Döring (ZND) Structure

The Zel'dovich, von Neumann, Döring (ZND) structure is used to describe the structure of a detonation wave. The name ascribed to the detonation structure is derived from Yakov B. Zel'dovich (1914-1987), John von Neumann (1903-1957), and Werner Döring (1911-2006), who conducted pioneering research into the structure of detonation waves. Although it is thought that they were at the time unaware of each other's work, the combined results of their research led to the explicit description of the detonation structure still used today [57].

The ZND structure essentially consists of a leading shock wave, which produces an adiabatic compression of the gas, coupled to a reaction zone, in which the gas ignites and products are formed. An example of the ZND structure can be seen in Figure 2.1 below.

FIGURE 2.1: ZND Structure of a detonation wave [57].

On the left-hand side of Figure 2.1 the gas is at rest and initial conditions. A leading shock wave, travelling at supersonic velocities, increases the temperature, pressure, and density of the gas nearly instantaneously. Behind the shock wave, an *induction zone* is formed, in which reactions take place within the mixture and radicals necessary for ignition are formed and begin to accumulate. The state of the gas in the induction zone is termed the *von Neumann state*. After the ignition delay time has passed the mixture ignites. A reaction zone is formed, in which the products are formed and heat is released, leading to another temperature increase. The pressure and density decrease across the reaction zone as the gas expands. Behind the reaction zone is the *Chapman-Jouguet state*, defined by a local Mach number equal to unity ($M_{CJ} = 1$).

2.1.2 Basic Equations

The von Neumann and Chapman-Jouguet states, as described by the ZND detonation structure, can be determined by considering the algebraic expressions, which relate the downstream state of the gas to the upstream state and the detonation Mach number. The relationships can be plotted in a graph in the form of the *Rayleigh line* and *Hugoniot curve*. The individual expressions are derived by finding the solutions to the steady, one-dimensional conservation equations across the wave. The solutions to the conservation equations are valid for both steadily propagating deflagration and detonation waves. A thorough derivation is presented in [57] and summarised in the following sections.

The first step is to define the basic thermodynamic and fluid quantities of the gas. The fluid velocity is defined as the sum of the product of the mean molecular velocity of the i th species and the partial mass density of the i th species, divided by the fluid density, and is given as follows:

$$\vec{v} = \frac{\sum_i \rho_i \vec{v}_i}{\rho} = \sum_i Y_i \vec{v}_i \quad (2.1)$$

The partial mass density of the i th species is $\rho_i = n_i W_i$ where n_i is the molar density of the i th species in the gas mixture, and W_i is the molecular weight of that species. $Y_i = \rho_i / \rho$ is the mass fraction of the i th species, where ρ is the density of the gas mixture given by $\rho = \sum_i \rho_i = \sum_i n_i W_i$. The mole fraction of the species can be similarly defined by the ratio of molar density of species to molar density of the gas, $X_i = n_i / n$ where $n = \sum_i n_i$.

The state of the gas can be defined by the following equation, under the assumption that the gas can be considered as a perfect gas mixture:

$$p = \rho R T \quad (2.2)$$

where p is the pressure of the gas, and the sum of the partial pressures accordingly, $p = \sum_i p_i$. T is the temperature of the mixture, and R the specific gas constant in $\text{Jkg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. The specific enthalpy of the i th species can then be defined as:

$$h_i = h_{f_i}^o + \int_{298}^T c_{p_i} dT, \quad (2.3)$$

where $h_{f_i}^o$ is the enthalpy of formation of the i th species and c_{p_i} is the specific heat capacity of that species. The specific enthalpy of the gas mixture is therefore the sum of the specific enthalpies of the individual species weighted by their respective mass fractions, $h = \sum_i Y_i h_i$. The specific heat capacity of the mixture can be defined similarly by $c_p = \sum_i Y_i c_{p_i}$.

The one-dimensional conservation equations can be defined using a moving co-ordinate system which is fixed to the wave, and shown in Figure 2.2. As such, all velocities are defined relative to the combustion wave. Here the subscripts 0 and 1 denote the upstream reactant and downstream product states, respectively. The conservation of mass, momentum, and energy equations, in their respective order, are given by the following equations:

$$\rho_0 u_0 = \rho_1 u_1 \quad (2.4)$$

$$p_0 + \rho_0 u_0^2 = p_1 + \rho_1 u_1^2 \quad (2.5)$$

$$h_0 + \frac{u_0^2}{2} = h_1 + \frac{u_1^2}{2} \quad (2.6)$$

FIGURE 2.2: Mass, momentum, and energy conservation equations across a combustion wave with moving co-ordinate system fixed to the wave. Subscripts 0 and 1 denote the upstream and downstream gas states respectively.

Splitting the enthalpy of formation from the sensible enthalpy (due to temperature changes), equation 2.6 can be rewritten as:

$$h_0 + q + \frac{u_0^2}{2} = h_1 + \frac{u_1^2}{2} \quad (2.7)$$

where q is the heat release and defined as the difference in the enthalpies of formation between the reactants and products of the gas and u_0 and u_1 are the upstream and downstream gas velocities respectively. The heat release can be calculated using the following equation:

$$q = \sum_i^{\text{reactants}} v_i h_{f_i}^o - \sum_j^{\text{products}} v_j h_{f_j}^o \quad (2.8)$$

where v_i is the stoichiometric coefficient of species i , and $h_{f_i}^o$ the enthalpy of formation. As the enthalpies of formation are included in the heat release term, the terms in equation 2.7 are the sensible enthalpies, which can be calculated by:

$$h = \int_{298\text{K}}^T c_p dT \quad (2.9)$$

The sensible enthalpy of the products and reactants can be defined, again assuming a perfect gas and $h = c_p T$. Using the relationships, $R = c_p - c_v$ and $\kappa = c_p/c_v$, the sensible enthalpy is given by:

$$h = \frac{\kappa}{\kappa - 1} \frac{p}{\rho} \quad (2.10)$$

The thermodynamic path along which the gas proceeds from the initial to the final state can be obtained by combining equations 2.4 and 2.5, yielding:

$$\frac{p_1 - p_0}{v_0 - v_1} = \rho_0^2 u_0^2 = \rho_1^2 u_1^2 = \dot{m}^2 \quad (2.11)$$

where v is the specific volume, as defined by the inverse of the density ρ , and \dot{m} is the mass flux per unit area. Rearranging equation 2.11 gives the following equation for the mass flux:

$$\dot{m} = \sqrt{\frac{p_1 - p_0}{v_0 - v_1}} \quad (2.12)$$

Equation 2.12, although simple, helps greatly in defining the possible states of the gas in both deflagration and detonation waves (the derivation thus far is valid for both). For positive \dot{m} values, i.e. real flows which are of interest, equation 2.12 can be used to define regions in a $p - v$ plane where real solutions to the conservation equations exist. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- If $\rho_0 < \rho_1$ (and as such $v_0 > v_1$) then $p_1 > p_0$.
- If $\rho_0 > \rho_1$ (and as such $v_0 < v_1$) then $p_1 < p_0$.
- In summary, an increase or decrease in gas density corresponds to an increase or decrease in gas pressure, respectively.

Defining the x co-ordinate as $x = \frac{v_1}{v_0} = \hat{v}$ and the y co-ordinate as $y = \frac{p_1}{p_0} = \hat{p}$ the behaviour outlined above can be clearly demonstrated in graphical form, as shown in Figure 2.3 below.

FIGURE 2.3: Real solutions to the conservation equations for deflagration and detonation waves. The red hatched areas are invalid solutions.

The valid solutions to the conservation equations, as shown in Figure 2.3, can be split into two distinct areas. On the upper left-hand side of the plot is the detonation domain, characterised by x values of less than 1 and y values of greater than 1. The x and y values correspond to increases in pressure and density across the detonation wave.

The bottom right-hand side of the plot is the deflagration domain, characterised by x values of greater than 1 and y values of less than 1. The x and y values correspond to decreases in pressure and density across the deflagration wave. The changes in state across a detonation and deflagration wave, as derived from the conservation equations in this section, confirm the behaviour and differences in detonation and deflagration waves as presented previously in Table 2.1.

2.1.3 Rayleigh Line

The conservation equations can be manipulated further to derive the aforementioned Rayleigh line and Hugoniot curve. Firstly, the speed of sound in the upstream state of the gas and the resulting Mach number are defined by the following equations:

$$c_0 = \sqrt{\frac{\kappa_0 p_0}{\rho_0}} = \sqrt{\kappa_0 p_0 v_0} \quad (2.13)$$

$$M_0 = \frac{u_0}{c_0} \quad (2.14)$$

Using equations 2.11, 2.13, and 2.14, equation 2.12 can be rearranged, resulting in the following expression:

$$\kappa_0 M_0^2 = \frac{y-1}{1-x} \quad (2.15)$$

Rearranging into the form $y = mx + c$ shows that equation 2.15 describes a straight line in the $x - y$ plane and is known as the Rayleigh line. It defines the thermodynamic path along which the state of the gas transitions, from $(1, 1)$ prior to the combustion wave, to (x, y) behind the combustion wave. The rearranged equation is given in equations 2.16 and 2.17 below.

$$y = -(\kappa_0 M_0^2)x + (1 + \kappa_0 M_0^2) \quad (2.16)$$

$$\hat{p} = -(\kappa_0 M_0^2)\hat{v} + (1 + \kappa_0 M_0^2) \quad (2.17)$$

The gradient of the Rayleigh line can also be written as

$$\left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)_{RL} = -\frac{y-1}{1-x} \quad (2.18)$$

2.1.4 Hugoniot Curve

The Hugoniot curve also relates the downstream state of the gas mixture to the upstream, pre-combustion state. Whereas the Rayleigh line only considers the conservation of mass and momentum equations, the Hugoniot curve additionally takes into account the conservation of energy equation.

Rearranging equation 2.11 gives the following expressions for the upstream and downstream gas velocities:

$$u_0^2 = \frac{1}{\rho_0^2} \frac{p_1 - p_0}{v_0 - v_1} \quad (2.19)$$

$$u_1^2 = \frac{1}{\rho_1^2} \frac{p_1 - p_0}{v_0 - v_1} \quad (2.20)$$

By substituting equations 2.19 and 2.20 into the conservation of energy equation 2.7, the velocities are eliminated from the equation and the Hugoniot curve is defined:

$$h_1 - (h_0 + q) = \frac{1}{2}(p_1 - p_0)(v_0 + v_1) \quad (2.21)$$

Assuming that the gas mixture is a perfect gas, the caloric equation of state, defined by equation 2.10, can be applied. The resulting equation for the Hugoniot curve is then expressed in terms of $\hat{p}(y)$ and $\hat{v}(x)$ only, instead of in terms of the enthalpy:

$$y = \frac{\frac{\kappa_0 + 1}{\kappa_0 - 1} - x + 2q'}{\frac{\kappa_1 + 1}{\kappa_1 - 1}x - 1} \quad (2.22)$$

$$\hat{p} = \frac{\frac{\kappa_0 + 1}{\kappa_0 - 1} - \hat{v} + 2q'}{\frac{\kappa_1 + 1}{\kappa_1 - 1}\hat{v} - 1} \quad (2.23)$$

where q' is the dimensionless heat release and is defined as $q' = \frac{q}{p_0 v_0}$.

The Hugoniot curve can be expressed in a simplified form as follows:

$$(y + \alpha)(x - \alpha) = \beta \quad (2.24)$$

where:

$$\alpha = \frac{\kappa_1 - 1}{\kappa_1 + 1} \quad (2.25)$$

$$\beta = \frac{\kappa_1 - 1}{\kappa_1 + 1} \left(\frac{\kappa_0 + 1}{\kappa_0 - 1} - \frac{\kappa_1 - 1}{\kappa_1 + 1} + 2q' \right) \quad (2.26)$$

The equation defining β shows that the Hugoniot curve has the form of a rectangular hyperbola. The equations obtained for the Rayleigh line and Hugoniot can be plotted on the same graph and used to determine the state of the gas mixture behind the combustion wave. Figure 2.4 below shows the Rayleigh line and Hugoniot curve.

FIGURE 2.4: Rayleigh line (—) and Hugoniot curve (—). The intersections between the two curves show the potential solutions to the conservation equations [57].

The valid solutions for a combustion wave are given by the points of intersection between the Rayleigh line and Hugoniot curve, shown in Figure 2.4. The type of combustion wave can be determined further by considering the detonation and deflagration regimes of the $\hat{p} - \hat{v}$ diagram, shown in Figure 2.3. The points of intersection are split into solutions representing strong detonation, weak detonation, weak deflagration, and strong deflagration.

2.1.5 Chapman Jouguet Theory

The previous sections detail the derivation of the Rayleigh line and Hugoniot curve, and how these two functions define the combustion wave configurations. However, considering only the Rayleigh line and Hugoniot curve does not fully define the combustion wave, as the gradient of the Rayleigh line is unknown. The resulting pressure and volume ratios of the detonation and deflagration waves are not explicitly known, as the points of intersection are dependent on the gradient of the Rayleigh line. This poses the question as to how detonation and deflagration waves actually appear in nature, and whether a definition can be formulated. The *Chapman Jouguet theory* (CJ theory) provides an approach for fully defining the combustion wave and therefore also the upstream and downstream gas states.

The CJ theory states that the Rayleigh line is tangent to the Hugoniot curve. The theory was developed by Donald Leonard Chapman and Ehrile Jouguet separately, each of whom used different justifications. Chapman postulated that since detonations produced experimentally were only observed to propagate at one velocity, the Rayleigh line must be tangent to the Hugoniot curve to produce a single solution. Jouguet on the other hand, postulated that the velocity behind the detonation wave must be sonic, which can be mathematically proven to be equivalent to the tangency condition [57]. The interested

reader is advised to refer to the literature for further details and the relevant derivations [57].

By applying the CJ theory, or tangency condition as it is also referred to, one single point of intersection between the Rayleigh line and Hugoniot curve results, as opposed to two points of intersection as in the detonation regime shown in Figure 2.4. The resulting detonation wave is known as *CJ detonation*. The CJ detonation can be seen in Figure 2.5 below. A *CJ deflagration* also results in the lower right region of the regime diagram.

FIGURE 2.5: CJ theory: the Rayleigh line (—) is tangent to the Hugoniot curve (—), with the resulting points of intersection known as CJ detonation and CJ deflagration [57].

2.2 Pulsed Detonation Combustion

The pulsed detonation combustion (PDC) engine is a concept in which combustion occurs as a detonation wave, as opposed to a deflagration wave which occurs in traditional combustion systems. Detonation waves travel at much greater velocities than deflagration waves and can therefore produce a much higher power output for a given heat release. Thermodynamically, PDC can be approximated by a constant volume cycle, or Humphrey cycle. Conventional gas turbines and aero engines are approximated by the Brayton cycle or Joule process. The Humphrey cycle has a greater thermal efficiency than the Brayton cycle for a given pressure ratio. This can be seen in Figure 2.6, where the pressure ratio is plotted against the x axis and the thermal efficiency against the y axis. The red line (—) depicts the Humphrey cycle and the blue line (—) the Brayton cycle. It is clear, that for a given pressure ratio the Humphrey cycle has a greater thermal efficiency than the Brayton cycle. As the potential further technical improvements to current gas turbines and aircraft engines are limited due to decades of continual improvement, the implementation of a new combustion system presents an opportunity to significantly increase gas turbine or aircraft engine efficiency and therefore potentially reduce emissions. The PDC concept is realised in so called *Pulsed Detonation Engines* (PDEs).

FIGURE 2.6: Thermal efficiencies for the Brayton (—) [8] and Humphrey (—) [16] cycles for a given temperature ratio, t .

2.3 Pulsed Detonation Engines

2.3.1 PDE Configuration

Pulsed detonation engines come in many different forms and concepts. The simplest of these consists of a constant area tube, which is filled with a fuel/oxidizer mixture as shown in Figure 2.7. An ignition system and valving is integrated in the engine to control the detonation process. These can be seen in Figure 2.7 at the inlet of the tube. Deflagration to detonation transition (DDT) devices are used to produce a detonation wave from the initial ignition. A nozzle can be positioned at the outlet of the tube if the PDE is to be used to generate propulsion, for example in aerospace applications. There are many technical challenges remaining in the development of a viable PDE concept, relating mostly to timing and reliable detonation initiation [77]. The transition from deflagration to detonation must reliably produce a detonation wave in every cycle. The control systems and timing are also very complex, due to the high velocities with which the detonation wave propagates.

FIGURE 2.7: Example of Pulsed Detonation Engine [77].

2.3.2 PDE Cycle

The pulsed detonation engine cycle consists of four main steps and is represented in Figure 2.8 below:

1. Initially, the tube is empty and at ambient conditions, denoted here by stage 1. Fuel and air are supplied to the detonation tube during the filling stage, as shown by stage 2.
2. The fuel/air mixture is ignited, shown by stage 3.
3. The detonation wave propagates along the tube and significantly increases the temperature and pressure of the gas, shown by stage 4.
4. The detonation wave reaches the end of and exits the tube, combustion products are exhausted and the tube then purged, resulting in ambient conditions in the tube, shown by stages 5-1.

FIGURE 2.8: Pulsed Detonation Engine cycle [77].

2.4 NO_x Formation Pathways

NO_x is formed via various reaction pathways depending on combustion parameters such as temperature, pressure, residence times, and species present. Traditionally, the formation of NO_x is attributed to four main mechanisms, the thermal or Zel'dovich, prompt or Fenimore, N₂O, and NNH mechanisms. Recently, additional mechanisms have been identified including reburn, DeNO_x etc. A brief explanation of the main NO_x formation mechanisms is provided in the following subsections.

2.4.1 Zel'dovich Mechanism

In his pioneering work into the formation of NO, Yakov Zel'dovich found that the formation of NO is determined by a set of highly temperature dependent reactions [99]. The mechanism is also known as the thermal mechanism, as formation of NO is dominated by the set of reactions at high temperatures. The Zel'dovich mechanism is defined by the following reactions:

The high temperature dependence of the Zel'dovich formation mechanism is due to the high activation energy of reaction 2.27. The activation energy is the energy which must be provided for the reaction to occur. As such, a large amount of energy is required for the first reaction in the Zel'dovich mechanism to occur. At very high temperatures, the required energy is provided and the reactions within the Zel'dovich mechanism progress very quickly, due to their high reaction rate coefficients [94]. The Zel'dovich mechanism therefore dominates NO formation at high temperatures.

2.4.2 Fenimore Mechanism

The Fenimore, also known as the prompt mechanism of NO formation is initiated by the reaction between hydrocarbon radicals (CH_n) and N₂. It describes rapid NO formation during combustion long before NO is able to be formed via the thermal mechanism. It is also commonly referred to as the Fenimore mechanism, named after C.P. Fenimore, who released a pioneering paper into the formation mechanism in 1971 [26].

Molecular nitrogen reacts with CH_n to form amines or cyano compounds [94]. As such, the Fenimore mechanism is prevalent under rich conditions during combustion. The following reactions describe the formation of NO via the Fenimore mechanism [94]. The initiation reactions required to form hydrocarbon radicals are omitted for simplicity.

The formation of NO via the prompt mechanism is typically observed within the reaction zone of a combustion process. In this region, there is an abundance of radicals as the gas reacts. The highest concentrations of the critical CH_n radicals are therefore located in the reaction zone, leading to a large NO formation via the prompt mechanism. Recently, the formation of NO via NCN has been added to the prompt mechanism [37].

2.4.3 N₂O Mechanism

The N₂O mechanism is relevant for the formation of NO under lean conditions and at low temperatures. The mechanism is defined by the following reactions [94]:

2.4.4 NNH Mechanism

Recently, the NNH formation mechanism for NO has been discovered. The mechanism is important for the combustion of fuels with large carbon-to-hydrogen ratios. The mechanism consists of two main reactions [94]:

Figure 2.9 shows a summary of the four NO formation mechanisms outlined in the preceding sections [50]. The plot in the figure is an approximate representation of the conditions under which each mechanism contributes most significantly to NO formation.

FIGURE 2.9: Schematic representation of NO formation mechanisms and the approximate conditions at which each mechanism is relevant [50]. ϕ is the equivalence ratio.

2.5 Calculating Fluxes

Integral to conducting a reaction path analysis is the calculation of fluxes between species. The algorithm developed and presented in this thesis employs numerical functions and routines to calculate fluxes between species of interest. Therefore, the underlying theory for the calculation of fluxes is outlined in this section.

Consider the following example reaction:

The molar flux of a certain species is defined as the rate of change of concentration of that species, given by the following general equation:

$$\frac{d[S]}{dt} = \nu_S w \quad (2.42)$$

where S is a species of interest, ν_S is the stoichiometric coefficient of the species being considered and w is the reaction rate, which is defined as:

$$w = k_f \prod_{j=1}^N [S_j]^{\nu'_{S_j}} - k_r \prod_{j=1}^N [S_j]^{\nu''_{S_j}} \quad (2.43)$$

where k_f and k_r are the forward and reverse reaction rate coefficients respectively and S_j the species concentration for the j -th species. ν'_{S_j} and ν''_{S_j} are the corresponding stoichiometric coefficients of each species on the reactants and products side of the equation,

respectively. The reaction rate has the same units as the molar flux of a certain species and is typically given in $\text{kmol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$.

Note that the convention regarding the stoichiometric coefficients assigns all reactants a negative coefficient and all products a positive coefficient. As such, the stoichiometric coefficients for reaction 2.41 are:

$$\nu_A = -2, \quad \nu_B = -3, \quad \nu_C = 4, \quad \nu_D = 5 \quad (2.44)$$

The molar fluxes of all species can then be defined using equations 2.42 and 2.43.

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} = -2k_f[A]^2[B]^3 + 2k_r[C]^4[D]^5 \quad (2.45)$$

$$\frac{d[B]}{dt} = -3k_f[A]^2[B]^3 + 3k_r[C]^4[D]^5 \quad (2.46)$$

$$\frac{d[C]}{dt} = 4k_f[A]^2[B]^3 - 4k_r[C]^4[D]^5 \quad (2.47)$$

$$\frac{d[D]}{dt} = 5k_f[A]^2[B]^3 - 5k_r[C]^4[D]^5 \quad (2.48)$$

By applying equation 2.42 to the following example reaction, the equations for the molar fluxes of intermediate species can be defined as follows:

where HCN and HCNO are intermediate species. The molar fluxes of these intermediate species are:

$$\frac{d[\text{HCN}]}{dt} = -k_f[\text{HCN}][\text{OH}] + k_r[\text{HCNO}][\text{H}] \quad (2.50)$$

$$\frac{d[\text{HCNO}]}{dt} = k_f[\text{HCN}][\text{OH}] - k_r[\text{HCNO}][\text{H}] \quad (2.51)$$

The algorithm uses the approach described above to calculate all molar fluxes between species. Equations 2.50 and 2.51 calculate the rate of change of species for one reaction, described by reaction equation 2.49. If the species being considered takes part in several reactions, then equation 2.43 is simply summed over all reactions involving the species:

$$\frac{d[S]}{dt} = \sum_r \nu_{S,r} w_r \quad (2.52)$$

where the subscript r denotes the reaction.

Chapter 3

Reaction Path Analysis Algorithm

3.1 Background

The development of an algorithm for carrying out a reaction path analysis is the main objective of this masters thesis. As outlined in Chapter 1, a novel approach for carrying out a reaction path analysis was developed and presented in a paper by Bohon et al. in 2016 [10]. An outline on the theory of reaction path analyses and the method developed by Bohon et al. is provided in Section 1.2.2. The algorithm developed within this work aims to expand on the work by Bohon et al. [10]. The algorithm was developed using the high-level, interpreted, programming language *Python 3.6*. The open source chemical kinetics software *Cantera* was used as a library for calculating all kinetic variables. Originally, the element tracing method was developed to be applicable only to one chemical kinetic reaction mechanism, developed by Bohon et al. The results produced by the application of the element tracing method provide insight into the various contributions from individual sub-mechanisms and generally highlight the potential of the method for conducting reaction path analyses. However, a greater accuracy in the prediction of target species formation is desired. The algorithm developed in this work aims to address both limitations. Firstly, it has been developed to be able to be applied to any reaction mechanism. Secondly, the accuracy of the predicted target species formation is improved. The following chapter is intended to provide a detailed explanation of the algorithm developed as part of this masters thesis.

The element tracing method, developed by Bohon et al. [10], allows the total flux into (from here on referred to as *inflow fluxes*) and out of (from here on referred to as *outflow fluxes*) a certain species to be distributed among multiple sub-mechanisms. In this way, the contributions to the net formation of a given species from different sub-mechanisms can be determined. The method can therefore be applied in a reaction path analysis to determine the contributions of different sub-mechanisms to the formation of a species such as NO.

The method assumes a large Damköhler Number, meaning that the characteristic chemical time scale is much smaller than the characteristic flow time scale. This assumption means that reactions progress quickly compared to any flow phenomena and the approach of summing fluxes in and out of species can be applied. The assumption is relaxed slightly to allow for the calculation of source and pool terms, which are detailed in later sections.

As a result, the proportion of total outflow flux of a species due to a certain sub-mechanism is equal to the proportion of total inflow flux of that species due to the same sub-mechanism.

The proportion is defined as the allocation factor, and described in more detail in the following sections. Starting with an initiating reactant such as N_2 , the fluxes between all relevant species within the reaction mechanism can then be calculated and distributed among the sub-mechanisms defined. Finally, once all fluxes between all intermediate species are known, the total inflow and outflow fluxes, and therefore the net rate of production of the target species can be calculated. Repeating the calculation procedure at each simulation position results in the rate of production of the target species and the relative contributions from each sub-mechanism to that rate of production. An example of the application of the element tracing method for a reaction path analysis tracing NO can be seen in Figure 1.3.

The developed algorithm is a post-processing tool which can be utilised to conduct a reaction path analysis of an already simulated process. The algorithm can therefore be implemented for a spatially or time resolved simulation, for example a freely propagating flame simulation or detonation wave, in which the flame or wave is spatially resolved, or for a time resolved reactor simulation. The developed algorithm was validated using the results from flame simulations from the literature. Therefore, the following sections use the example of a flame simulation as the input for the developed algorithm, and thus reference flame positions. Timesteps are also applicable where flame positions are mentioned, and other combustion processes are applicable where flames are referred to.

3.2 Methodology

The methodology used by the developed algorithm to carry out a reaction path analysis can be summarised by the following steps:

I. Input simulation results.

The simulation for which the reaction path analysis is to be conducted is provided as an input to the algorithm. The input is in the form of a csv file, containing parameters to fully define the gas state at all flame positions.

II. Define the tracing element, target species, and intermediate species.

For example, for a NO_x reaction path analysis, the target species is typically NO and the tracing element N.

III. Define initiation reactions and sub-mechanisms.

Define the initiation reactions for each sub-mechanism.

IV. Create network.

Create a network of reactions for each sub-mechanism by tracing the tracing element from the initiation reaction, through all intermediate species, to the target species.

V. Analyse flame positions.

Iterate through each flame position and calculate the fluxes between all of the individual intermediate species within each sub-mechanism. Sum all fluxes to calculate the total net flux to the target species at each flame position.

VI. Iterate reaction path analysis.

Iterate Step V. until the reaction path analysis solution converges.

Figure 3.1 shows a schematic representation of the methodology implemented by the algorithm for conducting the reaction path analysis. While the complete algorithm is a

FIGURE 3.1: Flowchart of reaction path analysis algorithm.

post-processing tool for reaction path analyses, it itself is comprised of pre-processing and processing steps as shown in Figure 3.1.

Steps I. to IV. are pre-processing steps, where the algorithm calculates global variables and parameters which are constant for all flame positions. In Step V., the algorithm iterates through all flame positions, calculating the molar fluxes between all intermediate species. There are several complex tasks and subtasks involved with carrying out Step V., which are covered in detail in Section 3.4. Once Step V. has been carried out, an initial result for the reaction path analysis, similar to the example shown in Figure 3.2a, is obtained. A number of simplifications and approximations are necessary for the first iteration, which are detailed in the following sections. Step V. is therefore subsequently repeated until a specified convergence criterion is met and a final result generated. The iteration is represented by Step VI. An example of the iterative results of the reaction path analysis is shown in Figure 3.2. It can be seen that the sub-mechanism profiles change between iterations, especially for the prompt sub-mechanism, between iterations 1 and 2. The final desired result of the reaction path analysis is shown in Figure 3.2d where the solution has converged.

The following sections detail the calculation steps and theory implemented by the algorithm. A top-down approach is used, whereby the main steps are described first, before the corresponding tasks and subtasks are detailed. The intention is to give the reader a clear overview of the main functionality and purpose of the developed algorithm, before providing the relevant calculation procedures required for all relevant tasks and subtasks. In Section 3.3, the four pre-processing steps defined in Figure 3.1 are detailed further. Thereafter, in Section 3.4, the tasks and subtasks associated with the two algorithm processing steps from Figure 3.1 are covered in detail.

FIGURE 3.2: Reaction path analysis of a freely propagating, stoichiometric methane flame conducted using the developed algorithm. Iterations 1-4 are shown in Figures (a)-(d) respectively. There is no difference between the sub-mechanism contributions in iterations 3 and 4 as the solution converges.

3.3 Algorithm Pre-Processing

The following subsections detail the four algorithm pre-processing steps (Algorithm Steps I. - IV.).

3.3.1 Input Simulation Results (Algorithm Step I.)

To carry out a reaction path analysis, the algorithm requires an input file in csv format which fully defines the gas state at each flame position. The properties required are position, pressure, velocity (flame speed or detonation wave velocity), and temperature. Additionally, the mole fraction of each species at each position must be provided. The species should be written as they are defined in the chemical kinetic reaction mechanism, e.g. lower or upper case. An example of an input file is shown in Figure 3.3. The chemical kinetic reaction mechanism with which the simulation was carried out must also be provided as an input for the algorithm. The algorithm can then fully calculate the state of the gas at each flame position and calculate all kinetic properties, such as reaction rates using the gas state and Cantera functions.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	x	0	4.97135	7.357598	9.743846	9.843273	9.892986	9.917843
2	P	0.9999997	0.9999997	0.9999997	0.9999997	0.9999997	0.9999997	0.9999997
3	u	52.963	52.94533	52.9369	52.93348	52.94637	52.98202	53.05199
4	T	373	372.8755	372.8159	372.7576	372.7659	372.8351	373.0802
5	h	4.53E-33	6.54E-31	-3.54E-24	-2.43E-17	3.12E-18	8.59E-18	7.53E-17
6	h2	4.91E-11	1.12E-08	9.14E-07	0.00010015	0.00033874	0.00086375	0.00157232
7	o	-1.74E-23	-9.53E-21	-3.81E-17	-1.04E-13	5.87E-13	4.70E-12	1.73E-11
8	o2	0.1900452	0.1900452	0.1900451	0.1900264	0.189981	0.1898794	0.1897357
9	oh	-1.14E-25	-6.35E-23	-1.84E-19	-4.78E-16	2.74E-15	2.52E-14	1.41E-13
10	oh*	-2.61E-49	-1.46E-46	1.01E-43	-1.23E-38	5.40E-37	3.45E-34	3.06E-32
11	h2o	2.94E-15	2.24E-12	6.06E-10	2.21E-07	1.98E-06	1.29E-05	4.93E-05
12	n2	0.7149321	0.7149321	0.7149315	0.7148607	0.7146902	0.7143129	0.7137969
13	ho2	2.14E-18	1.83E-15	5.59E-13	2.30E-10	2.67E-09	1.95E-08	8.21E-08
14	h2o2	1.04E-18	8.96E-16	2.75E-13	1.14E-10	1.14E-09	8.28E-09	3.49E-08
15	ar	1E-09	1E-09	1.00E-09	1.00E-09	1.00E-09	9.99E-10	9.98E-10
16	co	1.33E-16	1.15E-13	3.51E-11	1.45E-08	1.45E-07	1.05E-06	4.42E-06

FIGURE 3.3: Example of csv input file for algorithm. The columns represent the flame positions and the rows represent the various properties whereby the gas composition is defined by the mole fractions of all species.

3.3.2 Tracing Element, Target & Intermediate Species (Algorithm Step II.)

The scope of this thesis focuses and limits the reaction path analysis to NO formation in deflagration and detonation processes. Therefore, the target species and tracing element are NO and N respectively. However, the algorithm has been developed such that other target species and tracing elements could be defined. The reaction path analysis of other target species allows the algorithm to be utilised for other analyses in future work. For example, a potential application is its implementation for the analysis of fuel decomposition processes, where the target species and focus of the reaction path analysis is not on emissions, but rather on fuel molecules.

The intermediate species are defined as all species in the reaction mechanism which contain the tracing element, with the exception of any terminating species. The terminating species are the target species (e.g. NO) and the initiating reactant (e.g. N₂). For example, for a NO_x reaction path analysis intermediate species include HCN, NCN, NH₂, NH etc.

3.3.3 Initiation Reactions & Sub-mechanisms (Algorithm Step III.)

The number of sub-mechanisms to be analysed and the corresponding initiation reactions must be defined. Furthermore, it is essential to define a group of all reactions which act as initiation reactions for the process being analysed. The initiation reactions are all reactions involving the initiating reactant and any intermediate species. In the case of an NO formation analysis, where the initiating reactant is N₂, the initiation reactions are all nitrogen fixing reactions, which split the triple bond within the N₂ molecule and form intermediate species. The following reactions are examples of initiation reactions:

The correct definition of all initiation reactions within the chosen chemical reaction mechanism is important, as all initiation reactions which are not assigned to a specific sub-mechanism by the user must be grouped together in an *undefined* sub-mechanism. The algorithm automatically adds any initiation reaction not assigned to a sub-mechanism by the user to the undefined sub-mechanism. In this way, the total flux from the initiating reactant to all intermediate species is accounted for when conducting the reaction path analysis.

3.3.4 Create Network (Algorithm Step IV.)

Once the simulation results to be analysed have been input, and the target species and tracing element defined, the network of reactions for each sub-mechanism is created based on the user defined initiation reactions. The network of reactions is a collection of all reactions involving the tracing element, which take place due to the defined initiation reaction. For example, for the initiation reaction:

the following reactions would all belong to the network of reactions for the sub-mechanism, as the products of the initiation reaction continue to react, forming other intermediate species. At first, the initiation reaction leads to the formation of HCN and N. Subsequently, all reactions containing HCN and N are added to the network. The same is then carried out for any other intermediate species formed by reactions added to the network, e.g. CN and NCO in the example below.

Note, that the reactions listed are only an example of some of the reactions which would belong to the network of reactions, which would in fact include many more reactions.

The initiation reactions for each sub-mechanism are defined by the reaction number assigned to the specific reaction in the global reaction mechanism. Using the defined initiation reactions, the algorithm proceeds to create a reaction network for each sub-mechanism using the following procedure:

1. A network reaction list is created, initially containing only the defined initiation reaction for the sub-mechanism for which the network is being generated.
2. The products formed by the initiation reaction (e.g. HCN,N) are saved. Each product is then analysed further individually, for example starting with HCN. All reactions contained within the global reaction mechanism containing the identified species are searched for and saved to a list.
3. The algorithm loops through all of the identified reactions. Two checks are performed before the reaction in the current loop is added to the network reactions list. Firstly, the reaction is only added if it is not already in the network reaction list. The first check becomes more important later, when the same reaction may be identified multiple times, to avoid duplicate reactions in the network reaction list. Secondly, it must be ensured that other initiation reactions are not added to the network reaction list. Initiation reactions added to the network reaction list would have unintended consequences and lead to reactions belonging to other sub-mechanisms being present in the network of reactions. To avoid initiation reactions being added to the network reaction list, the algorithm compares the reaction being analysed to a list of all initiation reactions in the global reaction mechanism. The list of all initiation reactions is defined *a priori*, and detailed in Section 3.3.3.
4. According to the two checks performed by the algorithm and described in step 3) above, reactions involving the products of the initiation reaction are added to the network reaction list.
5. The algorithm then loops through the reactions added to the network reaction list and repeats steps 2) - 3) for each reaction. As such, all reactions which are identified as part of the sub-mechanism are added to the network until no new reactions are found involving the species produced by previously identified reactions.

3.4 Algorithm Processing (Algorithm Steps V.-VI.)

The following subsections detail the two algorithm processing steps (Algorithm Steps V. - VI.). The tasks and subtasks of Step V. are addressed afterwards.

3.4.1 Analyse Flame Positions (Algorithm Step V.)

Following the creation of the network for each sub-mechanism, the algorithm processing steps defined in Figure 3.1 are carried out. The steps are, *Step V. Analyse flame positions* and *Step VI. Solution converged?*. Essentially, the algorithm processing steps analyse all flame positions and compute the molar fluxes between all intermediate species, so that the net rate of production of the target species can be determined. The calculation is then repeated until the resulting solution converges, as described in Section 3.2.

The first algorithm processing Step is *Step V. Analyse flame positions*. In this step, starting with the first flame position, all flame positions are analysed iteratively. The molar fluxes between all intermediate species are calculated at each flame position and subsequently the contribution to the total rate of production from each sub-mechanism is determined. *Step V. Analyse flame positions* contains several tasks and subtasks, and is therefore detailed further from Section 3.4.3 onwards.

3.4.2 Iterate Reaction Path Analysis (Algorithm Step VI.)

The subtasks carried out within *Step V. Analyse flame positions* produce an initial reaction path analysis result. An example can be seen in Figure 3.2a. As defined within the algorithm methodology, Step VI within the algorithm processing set of steps is to iterate through all flame positions, repeating Step V including all tasks and subtasks, until the reaction path analysis solution converges. An example of the iteration of Step V to convergence is shown in Figure 3.2. At each new iteration, the subtasks within Step V, shown in Figure 3.4 are carried out in the exact same manner as described in the preceding sections. The only difference is the use of the newly calculated flux correction factors, which leads to the differences between two successive iterations of the reaction path analysis. The relevant equations for the application of the flux correction factors are detailed in Section 3.5.5, where the procedure for the calculation of source terms for each sub-mechanism is explained. Step V. is repeated until the resulting reaction path analysis solution converges to within a defined tolerance. The target fluxes (detailed in Section 3.4.7) for each flame position and sub-mechanism are stored in a matrix, FT_{it} , where it is the iteration number. FT_{it} is a $N_{fl} \times N_{sub}$ matrix where N_{fl} is the number of flame positions and N_{sub} the number of sub-mechanisms. Therefore, $FT_{it,fl,sub}$ is the target flux from sub-mechanism sub at the flame position fl . The reaction path analysis residual is defined as the maximum norm of the difference between the FT_{it} matrices of two successive iterations:

$$RPA_{res} = \|FT_{i+1} - FT_i\|_{max} \quad (3.12)$$

The reaction path analysis is complete when the residual defined by equation 3.12 is within a defined tolerance. The tolerance can be defined by the user and was set to $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the results presented in this work.

3.4.3 Analyse Flame Positions (Algorithm Tasks V.I. - V.V.)

As alluded to in Section 3.4.1, *Step V. Analyse flame positions* consists of multiple tasks and subtasks. The tasks and subtasks listed below are carried out at each flame position and summarised in the flowchart shown in Figure 3.4:

- V.I. Set the state of the gas.
- V.II. Calculate the global fluxes between all intermediate species and for all reactions in the global reaction mechanism.
- V.III. Calculate the molar fluxes between all intermediate species for each sub-mechanism.
 - V.III.I. Attribute flux from all initiation reactions to their respective sub-mechanisms. Iterate through all intermediate species, at each species calculating the following for each sub-mechanism before analysing the next species:
 - V.III.II. Calculate allocation factor for the species being analysed.
 - V.III.III. Calculate source and pool terms for each sub-mechanism.
 - V.III.IV. Update all outflow fluxes from the species.

V.IV. Sum the molar fluxes to the defined target species (e.g. NO) for each sub-mechanism. The result is the contribution from each sub-mechanism to the formation of the target species.

V.V. Tasks V.I to V.IV are repeated for each flame position. Once all flame positions have been analysed, the flux correction factors are calculated.

FIGURE 3.4: Algorithm processing tasks and subtasks. The steps listed represent the tasks and subtasks of *Step V. Analyse flame positions* from the methodology outlined in Figure 3.1.

Once all tasks and subtasks have been executed, the algorithm proceeds with Step VI from the algorithm process shown in Figure 3.1.

Tasks V.I. - V.IV. are repeated for all flame positions. As seen in Figure 3.4, Task V.III. consists of several subtasks, which are inherently complex and require iteration and the definition of a convergence criterion. The following subsections detail Tasks V.I. - V.IV. The Subtasks V.III.I. - V.III.IV. are then elaborated on in Section 3.5.

3.4.4 Set State of Gas (Algorithm Task V.I.)

For each flame position, the state of the gas is set using the information provided in the input file. The state of the gas is fully defined by setting the gas temperature, pressure,

and composition, which are all contained in the input file. The composition of the gas is defined using mole fractions for each species in the gas.

3.4.5 Calculate Global Fluxes (Algorithm Task V.II.)

The global molar flux is defined as the molar flux between two species over all sub-mechanisms. It is therefore the molar flux between the two identified species, over all reactions in the reaction mechanism. In the case of a reaction path diagram, the global flux represents the arrow between the two species and is defined as:

$$GF_{i,j} = \frac{d[S_i]}{dt} = \sum_r v_{S_{ir}} w_r \quad (3.13)$$

where $GF_{i,j}$ is the global flux from species j to species i , S_i is the concentration of species i , and $v_{S_{ir}}$ is the stoichiometric coefficient of species i in reaction r . The global flux is therefore the rate of change of concentration of species i from all reactions r in which species j is converted to species i .

The global fluxes between all intermediate species are therefore of importance as they are the basis of the reaction path analysis to discern the contributions to the global molar fluxes by each sub-mechanism. Consider the following simplified example illustrating the calculation of a global molar flux.

Assume the following reactions describe the reaction mechanism used for the simulation for which the reaction path analysis is to be conducted.

Consider the example of calculating the global molar flux between HCN and CN. Firstly, only the reactions within the mechanism which convert HCN to CN or vice-versa are considered. In the example above the relevant equations are therefore equations 3.16, 3.17, 3.18, and 3.19. Applying equation 3.13, the global flux between HCN and CN can then be calculated:

$$GF_{\text{CN,HCN}} = \frac{d[\text{CN}]}{dt} = \sum_{r=R3}^{R6} v_{\text{CN}} w_r \quad (3.22)$$

The global fluxes between two given species are therefore always equal in magnitude and opposite in direction as the depletion of one species leads to the formation of the other:

$$GF_{\text{CN,HCN}} = -GF_{\text{HCN,CN}} \quad (3.23)$$

3.4.6 Calculate Molar Fluxes (Algorithm Task V.III.)

The calculation of molar fluxes between all intermediate species, and the relative contributions to those fluxes from each sub-mechanism is the main component of the reaction path analysis. The calculation requires fluxes from all initiation reactions to be determined, along with allocation factors, pool terms, and source terms for each intermediate species and sub-mechanism. For the flux from species j , to species i , for sub-mechanism sub , the molar flux between two species for a specific sub-mechanism is defined as $mf_{i,j,sub}$. For example, $mf_{\text{CN,N,prompt}}$ is the molar flux from N to CN within the prompt sub-mechanism. As with the global fluxes defined in Section 3.4.5, the molar fluxes are equal and opposite, meaning that:

$$mf_{i,j,sub} = -mf_{j,i,sub} \quad (3.24)$$

As described at the beginning of this section, and shown in Figure 3.4, the algorithm carries out several subtasks as part of *Task V.III. Calculate molar fluxes*. The subtasks are:

- V.III.I Attribute flux from all initiation reactions to their respective sub-mechanisms.
- V.III.II Calculate allocation factor for the species being analysed.
- V.III.III Calculate source and pool terms for each sub-mechanism.
- V.III.IV Update all outflow fluxes from the species.

The subtasks V.III.II to V.III.IV above are detailed separately in Section 3.5.

1. Attribute initiation flux (Algorithm Subtask V.III.I.)

The molar fluxes are calculated between all intermediate species by iterating through all species and for each species calculating the outflow fluxes based on the inflow fluxes and the calculated allocation factors. Therefore, for each sub-mechanism, there must be at least one known flux between two species, so that the outflow fluxes can be calculated and the process of iterating through all intermediate species can be carried out. The known fluxes are in the form of the initiation fluxes, which can be attributed to their respective sub-mechanisms. Take for example the following prompt sub-mechanism initiation reaction:

Since the equation above is the initiation reaction for the prompt sub-mechanism, all of its flux is attributed to the prompt sub-mechanism accordingly. Therefore, referring to equation 2.42 from Section 2.5:

$$mf_{\text{NCN,N}_2,\text{prompt}} = \frac{d[\text{NCN}]}{dt} = v_{\text{NCN}}w \quad (3.26)$$

$$mf_{\text{NCN,N}_2,\text{prompt}} = k_f[\text{N}_2][\text{CH}] \quad (3.27)$$

Within the algorithm, the calculated flux, $m f_{\text{NCN}, \text{N}_2, \text{prompt}}$, is then stored in a molar fluxes matrix of all fluxes between intermediate species. The same calculation is then repeated for all initiation reactions, providing the known molar fluxes with which the iteration through all intermediate species can proceed.

2. Iterate through intermediate species (Algorithm Subtasks V.III.II. - V.III.IV.)

Once the flux from initiation reactions has been attributed to each sub-mechanism, the algorithm iterates through all intermediate species to calculate the molar fluxes between intermediate species and store them in the molar fluxes matrix. As an example, consider the prompt sub-mechanism. The corresponding reaction path diagram can be seen in Figure 3.5, which shows all intermediate species relevant to the sub-mechanism, and the flow of nitrogen from the initiating reactant, N_2 , through to the target species, NO . The radical species listed by each arrow linking intermediate species represent the reaction partners with which the species at the base of the respective arrow reacts to form the species at the arrowhead.

FIGURE 3.5: Example of a reaction path diagram for the prompt sub-mechanism [10]. The flux between intermediate species is represented by the arrows. The radicals represent the reaction partners.

The flux between N_2 and NCN is calculated during the attribution of initiation fluxes, and described in the example above. In the next step, the NCN intermediate species is analysed. The source terms, pool terms, and allocation factors for NCN are calculated according to the procedure and equations provided in Section 3.5. Finally, the outflow fluxes can be calculated, which in this example are the molar fluxes from NCN to HCN , CN , N , and NO . The next intermediate species, HCN is then analysed, where the same calculation procedure is applied, enabling the calculation of the outflow fluxes from HCN to CN , NCO , and NH . In this manner, all intermediate species are analysed, and as such the molar fluxes between all intermediate species are calculated successively. The iteration is then subsequently applied to each sub-mechanism.

In the example above, beginning with NCN , the intermediate species can be iterated through to finally obtain the net flux to NO for the prompt sub-mechanism. For an efficient calculation, the intermediate species would be analysed in the following order: NCN , HCN , CN , NCO , NH , N , NO . As the last calculation step for each intermediate

species is the calculation of all outflow fluxes, calculating the species in this order enables all required inflow fluxes for each species to be known quantities. Consider for example the intermediate species N from the above example. The inflow fluxes for N come from NCN, CN, NCO, NH. Therefore, these species must be analysed before N, which is achieved using the order described above. However, for more complex reaction path diagrams, it may not always be possible to iterate through all intermediate species in an order such that all inflow fluxes are known for all intermediate species. Consider the arbitrary example shown in the schematic in Figure 3.6.

FIGURE 3.6: Example of the flux between intermediate species. To calculate all fluxes (arrows) an iterative approach needs to be implemented.

The flux from N_2 to intermediate species A and B is known (initiation reactions). To calculate the flux from B to A, species B must be analysed using the procedure described above. Initially the flux from D to B is unknown, which is one of the inflow fluxes needed for analysing B. Therefore, the algorithm implements an iterative approach, where species B is analysed using the known inflow fluxes, namely the flux from N_2 in this example. As a result, the outflow flux from B to A, and from B to C will be calculated, after which the flux from C to D can be determined. Once all intermediate species have been analysed, and the respective molar fluxes stored in an initial molar fluxes matrix, the intermediate species are analysed again in a subsequent iteration using the fluxes calculated in the first iteration through all species. Therefore, in the subsequent iterations, there is an inflow flux from D to B which is considered when analysing species B. The resulting molar fluxes matrix is also stored and a residual, defined as the maximum norm of the difference of the two matrices, is calculated:

$$mf_{res} = \left\| \frac{MF_{i+1} - MF_i}{MF_i} \right\|_{max} \quad (3.28)$$

where MF_{i+1} is an $N_{intsp} \times N_{intsp} \times N_{sub}$ matrix containing the molar fluxes between all intermediate species for each sub-mechanism. N_{intsp} is the number of intermediate species and N_{sub} the number of sub-mechanisms. MF_i is the same matrix from the previous iteration. In this iterative approach all intermediate species are analysed until the residual converges to within a defined tolerance. For the results presented in this work the tolerance was set to 0.1%.

3.4.7 Sum Fluxes to Target Species (Algorithm Task V.IV.)

Once molar fluxes between all intermediate species, and for all sub-mechanisms have been calculated as per the procedure outlined above, the contributions from each sub-mechanism to the net rate of production of the target species are determined. The contribution from a sub-mechanism is defined as:

$$FT_{sub} = \sum_{sp} mf_{target,sp,sub} - \sum_{sp} mf_{sp,target,sub} \quad (3.29)$$

where FT_{sub} is the contribution to the net flux to the target species from sub-mechanism sub and $mf_{target,sp,sub}$ the molar flux from species sp to the target species for sub-mechanism sub . The first sum term in equation 3.29 is therefore the sum of all fluxes leading to the formation of the target species for the sub-mechanism being calculated. Analogously, the second term is the sum of all fluxes leading to the depletion of the target species for the sub-mechanism being calculated. Applying equation 3.29 to each sub-mechanism for a specific flame position gives the relative contributions from each sub-mechanism to the target species rate of production. The calculation is repeated at each flame position as per the flowchart in Figure 3.4.

3.4.8 Flux Correction Factors (Algorithm Task V.V.)

The last step within the algorithm processing set of tasks outlined in Figure 3.4 is *Task V.V. Calculate flux correction factors*. Once one complete analysis for all flame positions has been carried out, the results are used to calculate updated flux correction factors, which are used within each flame position to calculate source terms and allocation factors (detailed in Section 3.5). As outlined in Section 3.2, the reaction path analysis is conducted using an iterative approach. All flame positions are analysed in an initial iteration, whereby a number of necessary assumptions are made. In particular, during the first iteration of all flame positions, the flux correction factor for every intermediate species is equal, and simplified to $fc_{sp,sub} = 1/N_{sub}$. After all flame positions have been analysed, the contribution to the formation of each species by each sub-mechanism is used to update the flux correction factors for each species and sub-mechanism. The newly calculated flux correction factors are then used for the following iteration of the reaction path analysis through all flame positions. In this iterative manner, the flux correction factors are updated at the end of each iteration through all flame positions and used for the next iteration, until the solution converges to within a defined tolerance.

For a given species, the flux correction factor for a sub-mechanism is the sub-mechanism's contribution to the formation of that species. It is therefore the integral of the flux into the species across all flame positions analysed divided by the total formation of the species by all sub-mechanisms. Negative fluxes are not considered, as only the sub-mechanism's contribution to the formation of that species is to be calculated, and not its contribution to the depletion of the species:

$$fc_{sp,sub} = \frac{\int_{x_0}^{x_1} MF_{sp,sub} dx}{\int_{x_0}^{x_1} MF_{sp} dx} \quad (3.30)$$

where $fc_{sp,sub}$ is the flux correction factor for species sp and sub-mechanism sub , x_0 is the lower bound to the left of the flame, x_1 the upper bound at the maximum flame position,

$MF_{sp,sub}$ the molar flux to species sp from all other species for sub-mechanism sub , and MF_{sp} the molar flux to species sp from all sub-mechanisms. An example is shown in Figure 3.7, for the simple case where only two sub-mechanisms are defined and the flux correction factor for NO is calculated.

FIGURE 3.7: Representation of the calculation of flux correction factors. The contribution to the formation of a species (e.g. NO) is represented by the green hatched and blue areas for the prompt and thermal sub-mechanisms respectively.

The total species formation is represented by the red dotted curve (in this example for the NO species). The contribution of each sub-mechanism to the total formation of the species is represented by the hatched green and solid blue areas in Figure 3.7 and equivalent to the positive fluxes from each sub-mechanism integrated over all flame positions. The total species formation is the area under the red dotted curve, which is equivalent to the integral of the total positive flux from all sub-mechanisms over all flame positions. The flux correction factor for each sub-mechanism is then defined as the ratio of the contribution of the sub-mechanism to the total formation of the species being considered. The same approach is used for each intermediate species within the mechanism.

3.5 Calculate Molar Fluxes (Algorithm Task V.III.)

As alluded to in Section 3.4.6, the calculation of molar fluxes (Algorithm Task V.III.) between all intermediate species is complex and requires the most computational effort within the algorithm processing group of tasks. The calculation of molar fluxes requires additional subtasks to be performed, which are the focus of this section. The following terms must be calculated as part of the calculation of molar fluxes between intermediate species:

- Allocation factors, $\eta_{sp,sub}$ (Algorithm Subtask V.III.II)
- Source terms, $S_{sp,sub}$ (Algorithm Subtask V.III.III)
- Pool terms, P_{sp} (Algorithm Subtask V.III.III)

Once the allocation factors, pool terms, and source terms have been calculated, the outflow fluxes are determined, as defined by *Subtask V.III.IV. Update outflow fluxes*, which is detailed at the end of this section in Section 3.5.7. The following subsections provide an overview of the notation used for the calculation of molar fluxes, before detailing the underlying theory required for the calculation of the terms listed above.

3.5.1 Flux Notation

Before detailing the methodology applied for determining molar fluxes for all sub-mechanisms, the notation used and theory of calculating molar fluxes is presented. Firstly, consider a given intermediate species to be analysed, sp . The relevant total global inflow and outflow fluxes to and from species sp are defined as F_{sp} and G_{sp} respectively, and shown in Figure 3.8. The total global flux describes the sum of the global fluxes from all other intermediate species, i.e. the total flux leading to the formation of sp for the case of F_{sp} , or the total flux leading to the depletion of sp in the case of G_{sp} .

FIGURE 3.8: Representation of the total global inflow and outflow flux to and from a species. sp is the species, F_{sp} the total global inflow flux from all other intermediate species, and G_{sp} the total global outflow flux to all other intermediate species.

However, in almost all cases the total inflow and outflow flux will not be balanced and the concentration of species sp will either increase or decrease accordingly. To account for the imbalance between F_{sp} and G_{sp} , an additional *source term* S_{sp} is defined, such that:

$$F_{sp} = G_{sp} + S_{sp} \quad (3.31)$$

and shown in Figure 3.9.

FIGURE 3.9: Representation of the total global inflow and outflow fluxes and global source term. sp is the species sp , F_{sp} the total global flux from all other intermediate species, G_{sp} the total global flux to all other intermediate species, and S_{sp} is the source term such that the total flux into and out of species sp is balanced.

The total global fluxes are comprised of the individual global fluxes from the other intermediate species to and from sp , as detailed in Section 3.4.5 and calculated using equation 3.22. Figure 3.10 shows an example of how the total global fluxes F_{sp} and G_{sp} are comprised of many global fluxes between sp and the other intermediate species. $F_{sp,i}$ is the global flux from species i to species sp and $G_{sp,j}$ is the global flux from species sp to species j .

FIGURE 3.10: Representation of the global inflow and outflow fluxes of a species. sp is the species, B_1, B_2, \dots, B_n are the species with fluxes into sp and C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n are the species with fluxes out of sp . P represents the species pool term. $F_{sp,i}$ and $G_{sp,j}$ are the global inflow and outflow fluxes respectively.

The final distinction in fluxes regarding an intermediate species sp is to distinguish between the contributions to each global flux by the various sub-mechanisms. Indeed, this distinction is the goal of the reaction path analysis and final output from the algorithm

developed. Each link or arrow in Figure 3.10 represents the global flux between two intermediate species. The arrow is in fact comprised of the individual contributions from each sub-mechanism to that global flux, such that the sum of the contributions across all sub-mechanisms must equal the global flux between two species. The further distinction between molar flux contributions from each sub-mechanism can be seen in Figure 3.11.

FIGURE 3.11: Representation of the molar fluxes and contributions from each sub-mechanism. The different line styles represent the different sub-mechanisms. sp is the species, B_1, B_2, \dots, B_n are the species with fluxes into sp and C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n are the species with fluxes out of sp .

The inflow fluxes are denoted as $f_{i,sub}$ where i is the species which reacts to form sp and sub is the sub-mechanism index. The outflow fluxes are denoted as $g_{j,sub}$, where j is the species formed by the reaction of sp and sub is the sub-mechanism index. The different sub-mechanisms are shown by the different line types. The example shown in Figure 3.11 represents the fluxes for two sub-mechanisms (solid and dashed lines), however, the number of sub-mechanisms can vary.

The source term S_{sp} is defined as the difference between the total global flux inflow and the total global outflow fluxes of species sp , as defined by equation 3.31. The source term is also split into contributions from each sub-mechanism, $S_{sp,sub}$ where sub is the sub-mechanism index.

3.5.2 Flux Cases

The calculation of the allocation factors (Subtask V.III.II.), and source terms and pool terms (both Subtask V.III.III.) is dependent on the *flux case*, which is effectively a description of the state of each species. For example, the flux case describes whether the total inflow flux is greater than the total outflow flux of that species, i.e. the species accumulates, or vice-versa. The flux case dictates which fundamental equations are applicable for the calculation of the allocation factors, pool terms, and source terms. The parameters needed for determining the flux case of a species are described in further detail in the following subsections, but an overview is provided in Figure 3.12. The blue arrows represent the inflow fluxes, and the red arrows the outflow fluxes.

For a given species, the flux case is dependent on the direction of the net flux and whether or not the species has accumulated, represented by the pool term. The pool term, and

FIGURE 3.12: Schematic representation of flux case for a given species. F_{sp} & G_{sp} represent the global inflow and outflow fluxes of the species, sp , respectively.

how it is defined and calculated is detailed further in Section 3.5.4. If $F_{sp} > G_{sp}$, then species sp is being formed at a greater rate than with which it is depleted by. Species sp therefore begins to accumulate and the calculation of species sp follows the procedure for Case I. If $F_{sp} < G_{sp}$, then species sp is being depleted at a greater rate than with which it is being formed. A further distinction must be made as to whether the species has already accumulated in the combustion process/flame, represented by the pool term. If the species has accumulated, which can be due to the fact that $F_{sp} >_{sp} G$ at previous flame positions, then the pool term is positive, and Case II applies to the subsequent calculation of species sp . If species sp has not accumulated, and the pool term is therefore negative, then Case III applies.

3.5.3 Calculate Allocation Factors (Algorithm Subtask V.III.II.)

Where all inflow fluxes are known, an allocation factor for each sub-mechanism can be calculated. The allocation factor is needed to subsequently calculate the outflow fluxes of the species. The direction of the source term dictates how the allocation factor, $\eta_{sp,sub}$ is defined. First, consider the case where the total global inflow flux, F_{sp} , is greater than the total global outflow flux, G_{sp} , described by Case I in Figure 3.12.

Cases I: $F_{sp} > G_{sp}$

$$S_{sp} = F_{sp} - G_{sp} \quad (3.32)$$

$$S_{sp} > 0 \quad (3.33)$$

In this scenario, the source term is positive and an accumulation of the species being analysed, sp , occurs. The allocation factor for each sub-mechanism is defined as the ratio of the inflow flux to sp from the sub-mechanism to the total global inflow flux to sp . Let the allocation factor for this scenario be defined as $\gamma_{sp,sub}$, such that:

$$\gamma_{sp,sub} = \frac{\sum_i f_{i,sub}}{F_{sp}} \quad (3.34)$$

$$\gamma_{sp,sub} = \frac{\sum_i f_{i,sub}}{\sum_{sub} \sum_i f_{i,sub}} \quad (3.35)$$

Cases II & III: $F_{sp} < G_{sp}$

If the total global outflow flux is greater than the total global inflow flux, then the species is being depleted at a greater rate than at which it is being formed. While this phenomenon may seem impossible, it can occur in two different scenarios. Firstly, at various positions in the flame, where the total global inflow flux is greater than the total global outflow flux, the species will begin to accumulate. The accumulated amount, referred to as the pool term, can then be drawn from later in the flame at positions where $F_{sp} < G_{sp}$ (the total global outflow flux is greater than the inflow flux). This scenario is represented by Case II. Additionally, even if the species has not accumulated in previous flame positions, it can accumulate later in the flame and then be transported forward due to diffusion processes. The diffusion of a species forward in the flame is represented by Case III. Diffusion processes are especially relevant to deflagration flames and must therefore be

taken into account. The calculation of the allocation factor when the total global outflow flux is greater than the total global inflow flux of the species is defined by the following equations. The following calculation is valid for both Case II and Case III:

$$S_{sp} = F_{sp} - G_{sp} \quad (3.36)$$

$$S_{sp} < 0 \quad (3.37)$$

The source term is negative and therefore reverses in direction and points into the species sp , essentially acting as an additional flux in (refer to Figure 3.9). Let the allocation factor be defined as $\sigma_{sp,sub}$, such that:

$$\sigma_{sp,sub} = \frac{\sum_i f_{i,sub} - S_{sp,sub}}{F_{sp}} \quad (3.38)$$

$$\sigma_{sp,sub} = \frac{\sum_i f_{i,sub} - S_{sp,sub}}{\sum_{sub} \sum_i f_{i,sub}} \quad (3.39)$$

The calculation of the allocation factor is similar to the scenario where $F_{sp} > G_{sp}$, in that it is the ratio of inflow flux from the particular sub-mechanism being considered to the total global inflow flux. The only difference is that the source term for each sub-mechanism $S_{sp,sub}$ contributes to the inflow flux. Per definition, the source term $S_{sp,sub}$ will always be negative in this scenario and will therefore be added to the other fluxes in, $f_{i,sub}$, when calculating the allocation factor, $\sigma_{sp,sub}$. The calculation of the source terms is itself dependent on the flux case, and detailed in Section 3.5.5.

Cases I,II, & III:

By recognising that $\sigma_{sp,sub}$ will always be greater than $\gamma_{sp,sub}$ when $F_{sp} < G_{sp}$ and vice-versa, the calculation of the allocation factor, $\eta_{sp,sub}$ can be simplified by defining it as the maximum value of $\sigma_{sp,sub}$ and $\gamma_{sp,sub}$.

$$\eta_{sp,sub} = \max(\gamma_{sp,sub}, \sigma_{sp,sub}) \quad (3.40)$$

The allocation factor can therefore be calculated for all scenarios provided that the inflow fluxes into the species and the source terms are known. The calculation of the source terms is in itself complex and again dependent on the flux case. Accordingly, the calculation of source terms is addressed separately in Section 3.5.5.

3.5.4 Calculate Pool Terms (Algorithm Subtask V.III.III.)

Pool terms are required to calculate source terms and allocation factors. The calculation of pool terms is therefore detailed in this section before the calculation of the source terms is addressed. The pool terms represent the accumulation of species in various positions or times within the flame. For each flame position, the total global inflow and outflow flux of each species, and the corresponding global source term $S_{sp,sub}$, can be determined (refer to Figure 3.9).

Cases I, II, & III:

Consider what happens when the global source term is positive. The total global inflow flux is greater than the total global outflow flux of the species and as such, the species accumulates at the corresponding position in the flame. The pool term, P_{sp} is therefore increased by the source term multiplied by the timestep at that flame position, dt_i :

$$P_{sp}^i = P_{sp}^{i-1} + S_{sp}dt_i \quad (3.41)$$

where the P_{sp}^i is the pool of species sp at position i in the flame. P_{sp}^{i-1} is the pool term at the previous flame position. For a time resolved simulation, the timestep can be obtained directly from the simulation results in the input file. For a spatially resolved simulation, such as a flame simulation, the timestep is calculated using the flame (or detonation wave) velocity and the distance dx_i . The distance dx_i is defined using the midpoints between flame positions, such that:

$$dt_i = \frac{dx_i}{S_{L_i}} \quad (3.42)$$

$$dx_i = \frac{x_{i+1} - x_{i-1}}{2} \quad (3.43)$$

where x_{i+1} is the next flame position, x_{i-1} the previous flame position, and S_{L_i} the laminar burning velocity at the current flame position.

If the global source term is instead negative, which occurs when $F_{sp} < G_{sp}$, then the depletion of the species is greater than its formation and the accumulated concentration decreases. Equation 3.41 is still valid and used for the calculation of the new pool term, as the negative source term will result in a reduction of the pool term. One important note is the ability of the pool term to take on negative values. While not intuitive when considering the pool term as a concentration (which cannot be negative), negative pool terms can be explained by diffusion processes in the flame. A species which has been

formed and accumulated further downstream in the flame will diffuse forward in the flame where it may take part in reactions. Therefore, especially when analysing positions far upstream in the flame, where most species have not yet had the chance to accumulate, negative pool term values are common.

The following arbitrary example in Table 3.1 illustrates the calculation of the pool term for a species. Note that along with the global source terms, which can be different for every position in the flame, the timestep also differs due to the changing laminar burning velocity and unequal distance between flame positions (dx is typically not constant). The initial pool term of every species at position $x = 0$ will by definition be zero, $P_{sp}^0 = 0$.

TABLE 3.1: Example of the calculation of the pool term for a certain species throughout the flame. The net flux is multiplied by the timestep to obtain a contribution to the pool ($S_{sp}dt$) which is then added to the pool term value from the previous flame position.

x	S_{sp}	dt	$S_{sp}dt$	P_{sp}^{i-1}	P_{sp}^i
1	$-0.04\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3\text{s}$	0.5s	$-0.02\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$0\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$-0.02\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$
2	$-0.3\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3\text{s}$	0.1s	$-0.03\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$-0.02\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$-0.05\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$
3	$-0.3\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3\text{s}$	0.5s	$-0.15\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$-0.05\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$-0.2\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$
4	$-0.15\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3\text{s}$	0.2s	$-0.03\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$-0.2\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$-0.23\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$
5	$0.1\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3\text{s}$	0.3s	$0.03\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$-0.23\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$-0.2\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$
6	$0.3\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3\text{s}$	0.5s	$0.15\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$-0.2\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$-0.05\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$
7	$0.5\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3\text{s}$	0.5s	$0.25\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$-0.05\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$	$0.2\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3$

FIGURE 3.13: Example of the pool term for species N within a freely propagating, stoichiometric propane flame.

species is positive and N accumulates in the flame. At later flame positions, it can be seen that the pool term gradually increases towards zero, as the thermal NO formation mechanism dominates, producing NO and N.

In addition to the calculation of the pool terms for each species throughout the flame, the relative contributions from each sub-mechanism must also be determined. Regardless of whether the pool term increases (positive net flux) or decreases (negative net flux) at a certain position in the flame, the relative contributions to the change in the pool term by each sub-mechanism will generally not be equal. Consider the example in Table 3.2 where

Figure 3.13 shows an example of the pool term for N plotted for all positions in a flame simulation. In this case the pool term was plotted from a reaction path analysis of a freely propagating, stoichiometric propane flame simulation. It can be seen that the starting at zero, the pool term initially decreases due to a negative net flux and becomes negative itself. As detailed above, the negative pool term represents an amount of N formed later in the flame which then diffuses forward in the flame and reacts to form other species, therefore reducing the pool term at the earlier flame position (at a flame position of approximately 0cm in this example). At positions further along in the flame, the pool term increases as the net flux to the

TABLE 3.2: Example of pool term and contributions from each sub-mechanism.

x	$P_{sp,1}(kmol/m^3)$	$P_{sp,2}(kmol/m^3)$	$P_{sp,1}(kmol/m^3)$	$P_{sp}(kmol/m^3)$
1	10	15	25	50
2	20	20	30	70
3	30	30	40	100
4	32	35	43	110

the pool term of a species and the relative contribution from each sub-mechanism is listed for multiple positions in the flame. The values in the example are arbitrarily chosen for simplicity. The example shown is for the case where there are three sub-mechanisms. The contributions to the pool from each sub-mechanism are denoted as $P_{sp,sub}$ where sp is the species, and sub the sub-mechanism.

In an analogous approach to the calculation of the pool term for a species (equation 3.41), the individual sub-mechanism contributions to the pool term can also be calculated. Again, the flux case must be considered and the relevant calculation procedure applied as follows:

Case I: $F_{sp} > G_{sp}$

The species is formed at a greater rate than at which it is depleted. Therefore, the species accumulates, and the pool term increases, as defined by equation 3.41. The relative contribution to the increase in the pool term by each sub-mechanism is equal to the relative contribution of inflow flux by the sub-mechanism to the total inflow flux into the species, i.e. the allocation factor, $\gamma_{sp,sub}$. The contribution is then multiplied by the current timestep and added to the existing pool term for the sub-mechanism as follows:

$$F_{sp} = G_{sp} + S_{sp} \quad (3.44)$$

$$S_{sp} = F_{sp} - G_{sp} > 0 \quad (3.45)$$

$$P_{sp,sub}^i = P_{sp,sub}^{i-1} + \gamma_{sp,sub} S_{sp} dt_i \quad (3.46)$$

where $P_{sp,sub}^i$ is the pool term for the species sp and sub-mechanism sub at the current flame position, and $P_{sp,sub}^{i-1}$ the corresponding pool term at the previous flame position.

Cases II & III: $F_{sp} < G_{sp}$

The species is depleted at a greater rate than at which it is formed, and the pool term decreases according to equation 3.41. The contribution to the reduction of the pool term by each sub-mechanism is dependent on the relative sub-mechanism source term $S_{sp,sub}$. The calculation of the source terms for each sub-mechanism is detailed in the following section (3.5.5). Once the source terms are known, the contributions by each sub-mechanism to the pool term are calculated as follows:

$$F_{sp} = G_{sp} + S_{sp} \quad (3.47)$$

$$S_{sp} = F_{sp} - G_{sp} < 0 \quad (3.48)$$

$$P_{sp,sub}^i = P_{sp,sub}^{i-1} + S_{sp,sub} dt \quad (3.49)$$

where $P_{sp,sub}^i$ is the pool term for the species sp and sub-mechanism sub at the current flame position, and $P_{sp,sub}^{i-1}$ the corresponding pool term at the previous flame position.

3.5.5 Calculate Source Terms (Algorithm Subtask V.III.III.)

The preceding sections detail the theory of the calculation of pool terms and allocation factors for each sub-mechanism. Up until this point however, the calculation of the individual source terms for each sub-mechanism, $S_{sp,sub}$, has not been addressed. As evidenced by Equation 3.40, the source terms have a significant effect on the calculation of the allocation factors and therefore also on the calculation of all molar fluxes between species. Similar to the calculation of the allocation factors, $\gamma_{sp,sub}$, $\sigma_{sp,sub}$, and ultimately $\eta_{sp,sub}$, the calculation of the source terms for each sub-mechanism depends on the flux cases outlined in Figure 3.12. The following sections detail the necessary steps for calculating the source terms.

Case I: $F_{sp} > G_{sp}$

The ratio of the source term for a given sub-mechanism to the global source term is defined as being the same as the ratio of the inflow flux from a given sub-mechanism to the total inflow flux. The ratio was previously defined as $\gamma_{sp,sub}$ in equation 3.34 and can therefore be applied to the calculation of the source term, $S_{sp,sub}$:

$$S_{sp,sub} = \frac{\sum_i f_{i,sub}}{F_{sp}} S_{sp} \quad (3.50)$$

$$S_{sp,sub} = \gamma_{sp,sub} S_{sp} \quad (3.51)$$

where S_{sp} is the global source term for the species being analysed as defined in equations 3.31 and 3.32.

For the second case, where the total global inflow flux is less than the total global outflow flux, the calculation of the source terms also depends on an additional pool term, P_{sp} , detailed in the previous section (3.5.4) and flux correction factor, $f_{c_{sp,sub}}$.

Case II: $F_{sp} < G_{sp}, P_{sp} > 0$

For the case where $F_{sp} < G_{sp}$, the global source term, S_{sp} , will by definition be negative. Therefore, the accumulated pool of the species will be reduced as more of the species is depleted to form other intermediate species than is being formed.

When the pool term, P_{sp} , is positive, there is a surplus of the species and the species has accumulated. The negative global source term therefore reduces the surplus. The relative reductions due to each sub-mechanism are indiscriminate, meaning that the reduction of the pool term is split between the sub-mechanisms depending on their relative contribution to the pool term. Consider the following example consisting of three sub-mechanisms.

x	$P_{sp,1}(kmol/m^3)$	$P_{sp,2}(kmol/m^3)$	$P_{sp,3}(kmol/m^3)$	$P_{sp}(kmol/m^3)$
1	10	15	25	50

The source term for each sub-mechanism is defined as:

$$S_{sp,sub} = \frac{P_{sp,sub}}{P_{sp}} S_{sp} \quad (3.52)$$

For the example above, and assuming an arbitrary example source term, $S_{sp} = -20 \text{ kmol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, the resulting source terms would be as follows:

$$S_{sp,1} = \frac{P_{sp,1}}{P_{sp}} S_{sp} \quad (3.53)$$

$$S_{sp,1} = \frac{10}{50} (-20 \text{ kmol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}) \quad (3.54)$$

$$S_{sp,1} = -4 \text{ kmol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (3.55)$$

$$(3.56)$$

$$S_{sp,2} = \frac{P_{sp,2}}{P_{sp}} S_{sp} \quad (3.57)$$

$$S_{sp,2} = \frac{15}{50} (-20 \text{ kmol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}) \quad (3.58)$$

$$S_{sp,2} = -6 \text{ kmol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (3.59)$$

$$(3.60)$$

$$S_{sp,3} = \frac{P_{sp,3}}{P_{sp}} S_{sp} \quad (3.61)$$

$$S_{sp,3} = \frac{25}{50} (-20 \text{ kmol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}) \quad (3.62)$$

$$S_{sp,3} = -10 \text{ kmol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (3.63)$$

Case III: $F_{sp} < G_{sp}, P_{sp} < 0$

The final scenario to consider is when the global source term, S_{sp} , and the pool term, P_{sp} , are negative. This case results when the species draws from an accumulated species pool which has diffused forward in the flame. As opposed to Case II, where the individual sub-mechanism contributions to the species pool term are used to distribute the species source term between all sub-mechanisms, in Case III there is no information with which to distribute the global source term, S_{sp} . The flux correction factor, $f_{c_{sp,sub}}$ is therefore introduced and utilised to distribute S_{sp} as follows:

$$S_{sp,sub} = f_{c_{sp,sub}} S_{sp} \quad (3.64)$$

where $f_{c_{sp,sub}}$ is the flux correction factor for species, sp , and sub-mechanism, sub . For the initial iteration through all flame positions, all flux correction factors simplify to $f_{c_{sp,sub}} = \frac{1}{N_{submech}}$. For example, consider the same source term of $S_{sp} = -20 \text{ kmol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ as in the example above for the calculation of an initial iteration. As the pool term, P_{sp} is negative, the individual contributions to the pool term cannot be used to calculate the

source terms as above. The source term is distributed evenly among all sub-mechanisms for the initial iteration through the flame:

$$S_{sp,sub} = \frac{1}{N_{sub}} S_{sp} \quad (3.65)$$

$$S_{sp,1} = S_{sp,2} = S_{sp,3} = \frac{1}{3} (-20 \text{ kmol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}) = -6.33 \text{ kmol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (3.66)$$

The even distribution of source terms when $S_{sp} < 0$ and $P_{sp} < 0$ is therefore a simplification to enable an initial calculation for all flame positions. Once the algorithm has calculated all flame positions, the flux correction factors are updated according to the procedure detailed in Section 3.4.8 for each species and sub-mechanism. The updated flux correction factors are then used to calculate the source terms when $S_{sp} < 0$ and $P_{sp} < 0$ (flux Case III) in all subsequent iterations through the flame.

3.5.6 Summary of Calculation (Algorithm Subtasks V.III.II. - V.III.III.)

The preceding sections detail the method of calculation of the allocation factors, pool terms, and source terms for a species dependent on the relevant flux case as outlined in Figure 3.12. Table 3.3 summarises the equations applicable to each flux case.

TABLE 3.3: Summary of the relevant equations for calculating allocation factors, pool terms, and source terms for all flux cases.

Flux Case	Allocation Factor	Pool Term	Source Term
<p>CASE I</p> <p>$P_{sp,sub} < 0, P_{sp,sub} > 0$</p>	$\eta_{sp,sub} = \gamma_{sp,sub}$ $\gamma_{sp,sub} = \frac{\sum_i f_{i,sub}}{F_{sp}}$	$P_{sp,sub}^i = P_{sp,sub}^{i-1} + \gamma_{sp,sub} S_{sp} dt_i$	$S_{sp,sub} = \gamma_{sp,sub} S_{sp}$
<p>CASE II</p> <p>$P_{sp,sub} > 0$</p>	$\eta_{sp,sub} = \sigma_{sp,sub}$ $\sigma_{sp,sub} = \frac{\sum_i f_{i,sub} - S_{sp,sub}}{F_{sp}}$	$P_{sp,sub}^i = P_{sp,sub}^{i-1} + S_{sp,sub} dt_i$	$S_{sp,sub} = \frac{P_{sp,sub}}{P_{sp}} S_{sp}$
<p>CASE III</p> <p>$P_{sp,sub} < 0$</p>	$\eta_{sp,sub} = \sigma_{sp,sub}$ $\sigma_{sp,sub} = \frac{\sum_i f_{i,sub} - S_{sp,sub}}{F_{sp}}$	$P_{sp,sub}^i = P_{sp,sub}^{i-1} + S_{sp,sub} dt_i$	$S_{sp,sub} = f_{c_{sp,sub}} S_{sp}$

3.5.7 Update Outflow Fluxes (Algorithm Subtask V.III.IV.)

Where all inflow fluxes into a species, $f_{i,sub}$, are known, all outflow fluxes of the species, $g_{j,sub}$ can be calculated using the allocation factor, $\eta_{sp,sub}$, and the known inflow fluxes.

Generally, the outflow flux of a species for a specific sub-mechanism is simply the global flux out multiplied by the allocation factor for the sub-mechanism.

$$g_{j,sub} = \eta_{sp,sub} GF_{j,sp} \quad (3.67)$$

where $g_{j,sub}$ is the outflow flux from the species being analysed to species j for sub-mechanism sub and $GF_{sp,j}$ is the global flux from the species being analysed to species j . For example, if the molar flux from HCN to CN for sub-mechanism 2 is to be calculated, then the global flux between the two species, $GF_{CN,HCN}$ is multiplied by the allocation factor for HCN and sub-mechanism 2, $\eta_{HCN,2}$.

However, a further distinction must be made for the case in which any initiation reactions contribute to the flux between the two species being analysed. In this case, the flux due to initiation reactions is first subtracted from the global flux. The resulting flux is then multiplied by the corresponding allocation factor before adding the any flux from initiation reactions for the sub-mechanism being analysed. The procedure is defined by the following equations:

$$GF'_{j,sp} = GF_{sp,j} - \sum_{sub} fi_{j,sp,sub} \quad (3.68)$$

$$g_{j,sub} = \eta_{sp,sub} GF'_{j,sp} + fi_{j,sp,sub} \quad (3.69)$$

where $fi_{j,sp,sub}$ is the flux from species sp to species j from initiation reactions from the sub sub-mechanism. The calculation defined by equations 3.68 and 3.69 is shown schematically for an example with two sub-mechanisms in Figure 3.14 below.

FIGURE 3.14: Calculate outflow fluxes from species sp . The black arrow represents the global flux from sp to C_n and the red arrows represent the flux from initiation reactions between the two species. The different line types represent flux from different sub-mechanisms.

The global flux from sp to C_n is represented by the black arrow and has a flux of 100 units, chosen arbitrarily for simplicity in this example. Initiation reactions from sub-mechanism 1 (—) contribute 20 units from sp to C_n and 10 units in the opposite direction. Initiation reactions from sub-mechanism 2 (- - -) contribute 20 units from sp to C_n . The flux from initiation reactions does not need to be shared between the various sub-mechanisms as it by definition belongs to only one sub-mechanism and its net contribution can therefore be removed from the global flux. Equation 3.68 computes how much of the global flux between the species being analysed needs to be distributed between the sub-mechanisms. Initiation fluxes acting in the same direction as the global flux are defined as positive,

and fluxes in the opposite direction as negative. For this example, assume the following allocation factors for species, sp: $\eta_{sp,1} = 0.7$, $\eta_{sp,2} = 0.3$. By applying equations 3.68 and 3.69, the fluxes from Sp to C_n for each sub-mechanism are calculated in the following set of equations. Units have been omitted for simplicity.

$$G'_{C_n,sp} = G_{C_n,sp} - \sum_{sub} f i_{C_n,sp,sub} \quad (3.70)$$

$$G'_{C_n,sp} = 100 - \sum (20, -10, 20) \quad (3.71)$$

$$G'_{C_n,sp} = 100 - 30 = 70 \quad (3.72)$$

$$g_{C_n,1} = \eta_{C_n,1} G'_{C_n,sp} + f i_{C_n,sp,1} \quad (3.73)$$

$$g_{C_n,1} = 0.7(70) + 10 \quad (3.74)$$

$$g_{C_n,1} = 59 \quad (3.75)$$

$$g_{C_n,2} = \eta_{C_n,2} G'_{C_n,sp} + f i_{C_n,sp,2} \quad (3.76)$$

$$g_{C_n,2} = 0.3(70) + 20 \quad (3.77)$$

$$g_{C_n,2} = 41 \quad (3.78)$$

The sum of the fluxes therefore equals the global flux between the two species but also accounts for initiation reactions as opposed to if the fluxes were simply calculated using only the allocation factors and the global flux, as defined by equation 3.67.

Chapter 4

Results & Discussion

4.1 Validation

The algorithm was validated by comparing the total NO formation using the algorithm to the NO rate of production using the *net_production_rates* feature in Cantera. The individual contributions from each sub-mechanism were then validated using data from the literature, and in particular from research conducted by Bohon et al. [9, 10]. All flame simulation results were obtained using the reaction mechanism developed by Bohon et al. [9] and simulated using CHEMKIN-Pro [1]. The developed mechanism was based on Aramco1.3 [70], with C3 chemistry sourced from Sarathy et al. [85]. The NOx subset of the mechanism is based largely on the mechanism developed by El bakali et al. [22], with some adjustments made to the rates for the prompt initiation reaction and reactions participating in the NNH formation [9]. The complete mechanism can be found as supplementary material to this work, as well as in [9].

4.1.1 Cantera Validation

To validate the algorithm with respect to the overall formation of NO, a reaction path analysis was carried out for the case with no defined sub-mechanisms. All nitrogen fixing reactions were therefore grouped together as initiation reactions in the undefined sub-mechanism. The initiation reactions are listed in Table 4.1 below. The results of the reaction path analysis are shown in Figure 4.1. The reaction numbers listed in Table 4.1 refer to the reaction numbers as defined in the reaction mechanism.

TABLE 4.1: Sub-mechanism initiation reactions for validation of reaction path analysis with Cantera.

Sub-mechanism	Name	Reaction #
1	Undefined	1609, 1618, 1619, 1622, 1631, 1632, 1633, 1634, 1635, 1657, 1658, 1696, 1702, 1705, 1715, 1720, 1721, 1723, 1741, 1742, 1749, 1768, 1769, 1779, 1782, 1783, 1785, 1787, 1800, 1801, 1803, 1804

The total NO rate of production is plotted on the y axis in $\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$ against the flame position on the x axis, in cm. The black circles (\circ) represent the NO rate of production at all flame positions calculated using the *net_production_rates* feature in Cantera. The blue curve is the contribution to the NO formation due to the specified undefined

FIGURE 4.1: Total NO formation for a freely propagating stoichiometric methane flame.

FIGURE 4.2: Deviation between total NO formation as calculated by Cantera and by the developed algorithm for a freely propagating stoichiometric methane flame.

sub-mechanism. The total NO formation from all sub-mechanisms is identical to the undefined contribution in this case. Qualitatively, it can be seen that the calculated NO formation using the algorithm shows good agreement with the NO rate of production using Cantera.

A quantitative analysis comparing the NO formation as calculated by the algorithm to the Cantera NO net rate of production was also conducted. The deviation between the two approaches was calculated at each flame position as follows:

$$dev_{\text{NO-ROP}} = \text{NO}_{\text{ROP,Cantera}} - \text{NO}_{\text{Total,Alg.}} \quad (4.1)$$

where $\text{NO}_{\text{ROP,Cantera}}$ is the NO formation as calculated by Cantera and represented in Figure 4.1 by the black circle markers (\circ), and $\text{NO}_{\text{Total,Alg.}}$ is the NO formation as calculated by the algorithm and represented by the blue curve. The calculated deviations for all flame positions are shown in Figure 4.2. It can be seen that there the total predicted rate of NO formation begins to deviate slightly between flame positions of 0-0.1 cm, reaching a maximum deviation of approximately $0.0005 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. At the corresponding region in the flame, the total rate of NO production is approximately $0.2\text{-}0.4 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The deviation is therefore three orders of magnitude smaller than the predicted rate of production and the accuracy of the algorithm satisfactory.

4.1.2 Comparison to Literature

The developed algorithm was validated using the results of work published by Bohon et al. [9, 10]. In their work, the element tracing method for conducting a reaction path analysis was presented and implemented for alkane and alcohol flames. The results from a stoichiometric, freely propagating methane flame were therefore chosen for the validation of the developed algorithm.

The methane flame simulation and resulting initial gas composition was defined by the following global reaction equation:

The initial gas conditions were $T_0 = 373 \text{ K}$, $P_0 = 1 \text{ atm}$, and an inlet velocity of 2.5 times the laminar burning velocity, $u_0 = 2.5S_L$.

Figure 4.3 shows the rate of production of NO and the corresponding contributions from each sub-mechanism for a freely propagating stoichiometric methane flame as determined by Bohon et al. [9]. To produce comparable results, a reaction path analysis was conducted using the developed algorithm and the sub-mechanisms defined according to the definition used by Bohon et al. [9]. The sub-mechanism definition can be seen in Table 4.2, which lists the reaction numbers for the initiation reactions of each sub-mechanism. The corresponding reactions are listed in Appendix A.

TABLE 4.2: Sub-mechanism initiation reactions for validation of reaction path analysis with data from the literature [9, 10].

Sub-mechanism	Name	Reaction #
1	Thermal	1782
2	NNX	1658, 1783, 1800, 1801, 1803, 1804
3	Prompt	1742
4	NO ₂ _Net	1716, 1795, 1796, 1797, 1653, 1654, 1655
5	HNO	1636, 1637, 1650, 1788, 1789, 1790
6	Reburn	1662, 1666, 1659, 1660, 1661, 1663, 1664, 1667
7	Undefined	1609, 1618, 1619, 1622, 1635, 1657, 1696, 1702, 1705, 1715, 1720, 1721, 1723, 1741, 1749, 1768, 1769, 1779

The complete results of the reaction path analyses conducted in the work of Bohon et al. and this research are shown in Figures 4.3 and 4.4 respectively. The reaction path analysis solution, as calculated by the algorithm, converged after four iterations through the flame (refer to Section 3.4.2).

The overall results of the respective reaction path analyses show good agreement. The total NO formation, as well as the individual sub-mechanism contributions exhibit the same behaviour in the results from the literature and from this work. The overall NO formation is dominated and can be described by three well-known and extensively studied sub-mechanisms. Initially, prior to the flame front, there is no formation of NO, as nitrogen is bound in stable N₂ molecules. Further along the flame, as the temperature begins to increase due to heat release from within the reaction zone, the NO formation fluctuates between small negative and positive values. Peak NO formation of approximately $0.45 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is then produced almost entirely by the prompt mechanism within the reaction zone of the flame. The contribution to NO formation by the prompt sub-mechanism occurs within a small zone. The NO formation then decreases rapidly, before levelling off to approximately $0.12 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, at which point the NO formation is dominated by the thermal sub-mechanism. Between the peak in NO formation due to the prompt sub-mechanism and the region dominated by the thermal sub-mechanism, the NNX sub-mechanism displays a significant contribution and produces the gradual decrease in gradient behind the reaction zone. While the other sub-mechanisms analysed and plotted in Figures 4.3 and 4.4 have smaller absolute contributions to the total NO formation in the flame, their behaviour is vital in accurately capturing the total NO formation within and regions in front of the reaction zone. In the results obtained from

the algorithm (Figure 4.4), the contribution from the undefined sub-mechanism is zero at all flame positions. Therefore, the initiation reactions defining each sub-mechanism adequately capture all of the NO production in the flame.

FIGURE 4.3: Reaction path analysis for freely propagating stoichiometric methane flame as calculated by Bohon et al. [9].

It is worth noting another key difference between the results of the reaction path analyses of Bohon et al. and the current work. The burnout sub-mechanism, represented by the cyan curve (—) in Figure 4.3, and defined in the work of Bohon et al. is notably absent from the results using the algorithm developed in this work. The burnout sub-mechanism was used to model the contribution to NO formation from any accumulated species within the flame. One such example is the accumulation of the intermediate species N early in the flame, which then oxidises later to produce NO. The burnout sub-mechanism does therefore not distinguish between the sub-mechanisms which led to the accumulation of a species, attributing the subsequent contribution to NO formation to the burnout sub-mechanism only. Ideally, the contribution to the total NO formation due to the oxidation of any accumulated species within the flame, should be attributed to the sub-mechanism which led to the accumulation of that species, or distributed among several sub-mechanisms dependent on their relative contributions to the accumulation of that species. The developed algorithm is able to track the accumulation of all species, and the contribution of each sub-mechanism to that accumulation, within the flame through the implementation of the pool terms. The theory is detailed in Section 3.5.4. The correct allocation of flux from accumulated species within the flame, to their respective sub-mechanisms is an advantage of the developed algorithm compared to the existing approaches found in the literature and implemented in the work by Bohon et al. [9].

Before comparing individual contributions from each sub-mechanism, the total NO formation as calculated by the algorithm was compared to the total NO formation calculated by Bohon et al. The total NO formation is defined as the rate of production of NO, determined by summing up the contributions from all sub-mechanisms. For an initial

FIGURE 4.4: Reaction path analysis for freely propagating stoichiometric methane flame as calculated by the algorithm.

qualitative comparison, the respective total NO formation from the algorithm and the literature, as well as the NO rate of production as calculated by Cantera, were plotted. The resulting profiles are shown in Figure 4.5. The black circles (\circ) represent the net NO rate of production, as calculated by Cantera. The blue dashed (---) and red (—) curves represent the total NO formation calculated by Bohon et al. and by the algorithm respectively. Figure 4.6 shows the deviation between the total predicted NO formation and the net NO formation as calculated by Cantera (\circ in Figure 4.5).

It is clear by referring to Figure 4.5 that the overall NO rate of production is better captured by the algorithm than the data from the literature. Especially in the region of maximum NO formation and where the NO rate of production begins to plateau, greater deviations between the data from the literature (---) and the NO rate of production (\circ) exist. The data from Bohon et al. captures the initial behaviour well, but then underpredicts the peak NO formation. After reaching a maximum, the data from Bohon et al. also decreases too greatly, underpredicting the NO formation as it flattens out. Conversely, the predicted NO formation calculated by the algorithm shows a good agreement with the NO rate of production across all flame positions. The behaviour and accuracy of the two methods of calculation presented are confirmed in Figure 4.6, where the deviations to the total NO formation as calculated by Cantera are plotted. The data of Bohon et al. (—) displays visible deviation to the NO rate of production, reaching a maximum of $0.02 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at a flame position of approximately 0.03 cm. The absolute deviation of the NO formation as calculated by the algorithm (—) is nearly constant at a value close to zero throughout the flame.

The comparison shows an immediate advantage of the developed algorithm over other existing methods for conducting reaction path analyses in the literature. Even before considering individual sub-mechanisms, and their contributions to the overall NO formation in the flame, the total NO formation is better predicted using the developed algorithm.

FIGURE 4.5: Comparison of the total NO formation prediction for Bohon et al. (---) and the algorithm (—). The black circles (o) represent the total NO rate of production.

FIGURE 4.6: Deviation between the total calculated rate of production of NO and the NO rate of production as calculated by Cantera for Bohon et al. (—) and the algorithm (—).

The following sub-sections examine the contribution of each sub-mechanism to the total NO formation in further detail, and compare the corresponding results from the developed algorithm to those from the literature.

4.1.3 Prompt Sub-mechanism

Figure 4.7 shows the contribution to NO formation by the prompt sub-mechanism as calculated by the developed algorithm (---) and by Bohon et al. (—). Qualitatively, it is clear that the general behaviour of the prompt sub-mechanism is captured similarly by both analyses. The prompt contribution as calculated by the developed algorithm is however slightly wider at small NO formation rates. The algorithm therefore predicts a small contribution to the NO formation by the prompt sub-mechanism at flame positions where the analysis of Bohon et al. predicts zero prompt contribution. The discrepancy is due to the missing burnout sub-mechanism as described above, in Section 4.1.2. At flame positions where the discrepancy between the developed algorithm and Bohon et al. can be seen, intermediate species which are formed by the prompt sub-mechanism and which have accumulated in the flame react further to ultimately form NO.

The prompt sub-mechanism is dominant within the reaction zone of the flame, where there is a large concentration of CH_n radicals present. The initiation reaction for the prompt sub-mechanism was defined by reaction #1742 of the chemical kinetic reaction mechanism:

The triple bonded molecular nitrogen reacts with CH radicals to form NCN and H. Figure 4.8 shows the reaction rates of reaction #1742, as well as of reactions #1729 and #1730. The three reactions considered are the dominant reactions containing the intermediate species NCN within the flame and explain the corresponding peak NO formation seen in Figure 4.7.

FIGURE 4.7: Comparison of the prompt sub-mechanism contribution.

FIGURE 4.8: Reaction rates for the dominant reactions featuring NCN.

Within the reaction zone, at flame positions of 0-0.03 cm, all three reactions progress rapidly, shown by the peaks in reaction rates in Figure 4.8. As reaction #1742 occurs rapidly, shown by the blue curve in the figure, NCN is formed at a high rate which then reacts further via the other two following reactions:

Reaction #1729 (4.4) converts the NCN formed into another intermediate species HCN, which subsequently reacts further to form other intermediate species and ultimately NO. Reaction #1730 (4.5) directly converts NCN to the target species NO. The reactions in 4.3, 4.4, and 4.5 explain the peak in NO production over a narrow distance within the reaction zone of the flame as there is a large flux from the initiating reactant, N_2 , to an intermediate species, NCN (reaction #1742), and onto the target species, NO (reaction #1730).

4.1.4 NNX Sub-mechanism

Figure 4.9 shows the contribution to NO formation by the NNX sub-mechanism as calculated by the developed algorithm (---) and by Bohon et al. (—). The results show good agreement, with no contribution to NO formation prior to the reaction zone, and a maximum contribution at flame positions between 0 cm and 0.1 cm, before gradually decreasing to a minimal contribution at greater flame positions. There is a noticeable discrepancy between the NNX contribution as calculated by the algorithm and the results of the work by Bohon et al. at flame positions between 0 cm and 0.3 cm. The discrepancy can again be traced back to the flux represented by the burnout sub-mechanism by Bohon et al. and detailed in Section 4.1.3 above. As with the prompt sub-mechanism, in the aforementioned region of the flame, which includes the reaction zone, reactions lead to an accumulation of certain intermediate species. The accumulated pool of species can then be drawn from at later flame positions and react further to form NO. The resulting flux contributing to the total NO formation is grouped together in the burnout sub-mechanism in the work by Bohon et al. A proportion of the described flux from

FIGURE 4.9: Comparison of the NNX sub-mechanism contribution.

FIGURE 4.10: Comparison of the NNX sub-mechanism contribution.

accumulated species should correctly be attributed to the NNX sub-mechanism, as reactions within the sub-mechanism will lead to the accumulation of certain species within the reaction zone of the flame. The described discrepancy seen between the two resulting curves in Figure 4.9 is therefore the proportion of the flux from the burnout mechanism which should correctly be attributed to the NNX sub-mechanism.

Figure 4.10 shows the reaction rates of the defined initiation reactions for the NNX sub-mechanism and Figure 4.11 the reaction rates for all reactions involving N_2 and NNH.

FIGURE 4.11: Reaction rates for all reactions between N_2 and NNH for the NNX sub-mechanism.

It can be seen that there is a large flux leading to the formation of NNH within the reaction zone, which corresponds to the increasing contribution to NO formation by the NNX sub-mechanism for flame positions between 0 cm and 0.05 cm. Although the reaction rate of

#1783 increases to a very large value between positions 0 cm and 0.1 cm, the net effect on the production of NNH as an intermediate species is reduced due to other reactions in which NNH reacts back to form N_2 . The reactions which convert the NNH back to N_2 can be seen plotted in Figure 4.11. The net effect of all reactions producing and depleting NNH is represented in the figure by the black dashed curve (- - -), which matches the contribution to total NO formation by the NNX sub-mechanism seen in Figure 4.9.

4.1.5 Thermal Sub-mechanism

Figure 4.12 shows the contribution to NO formation by the thermal sub-mechanism as calculated by the developed algorithm (- - -) and by Bohon et al. (—). The results show good agreement, with little to no deviation visible between the two curves in Figure 4.12.

FIGURE 4.12: Comparison of thermal sub-mechanism contribution.

FIGURE 4.13: Reaction rates for the dominant thermal sub-mechanism reactions.

As detailed in Section 2.4, the well understood and studied thermal sub-mechanism consists fundamentally of the three reactions listed below and plotted in Figure 4.13.

The combined flux from the reactions 4.6, 4.7, and 4.8 represented by the black dashed curve (- - -) in Figure 4.13 accurately describes the total contribution to NO formation by the thermal sub-mechanism for flame positions greater than 0.05 cm. At these flame positions, the initiation reaction 4.6 forms a significant amount of NO directly as well as N which proceeds to form additional NO via the reactions 4.7 and 4.8. The peak in reaction rates seen in Figure 4.13 within the reaction zone at positions between 0 cm and 0.05 cm does not translate into any significant NO formation as the atomic nitrogen, N, which acts as a reactant in reactions #1612 and #1613, has not yet been produced by the thermal sub-mechanism initiation reaction (#1782). Therefore any NO formation due to reactions #1612 and #1613 at positions in the reaction zone, is likely to be attributed to other sub-mechanisms, such as the prompt mechanism.

4.1.6 NO₂_Net and HNO Sub-mechanisms

FIGURE 4.14: Comparison of NO₂_Net sub-mechanism contribution.

FIGURE 4.15: Comparison of HNO sub-mechanism contribution.

Figures 4.14 and 4.15 show the contribution to NO formation by the NO₂_Net and HNO sub-mechanisms, as calculated by the developed algorithm (---) and by Bohon et al. (—). It is clear that the two analyses produce almost exactly the same results with respect to the NO₂_Net and HNO sub-mechanisms. As its name suggests, the NO₂_Net sub-mechanism does not have a significant influence on the net production of NO. Indeed, referring to Figure 4.14, it is clear that the positive flux from the sub-mechanism is cancelled out by the negative flux. Although the NO₂_Net sub-mechanism does not have a net effect on the total NO formation, it describes the interaction between NO₂ and NO and is necessary to accurately predict the NO formation at flame positions before the reaction zone, around 0 cm. It may seem counter-intuitive that there can be any flux between NO₂ and NO prior to the reaction zone, as the fuel-air mixture has not yet reacted. However, the aforementioned diffusion processes which are relevant to deflagration flames in particular, allow for NO₂ and NO which has been formed in later flame positions to diffuse forward in the flame. Therefore, NO which is formed by other sub-mechanisms such as prompt and NNX in the reaction zone diffuses forward in the flame, where it is depleted and forms NO₂ via the reactions within the NO₂_Net sub-mechanism. The described depletion of NO can be seen in Figure 4.14 by the negative NO formation values at flame positions between -0.05 cm and 0 cm. The NO₂ formed then reacts back to NO via the NO₂_Net reactions, producing the following rise in NO formation at a flame position of approximately 0 cm. The depletion and subsequent production of diffused NO via the NO₂_Net sub-mechanism therefore completely describes the early behaviour in NO production within the flame, confirmed by the fact that the NO₂_Net sub-mechanism perfectly matches the NO-ROP curve for flame positions less than 0 cm (refer to NO₂_Net contribution in Figures 4.3 and 4.4).

The HNO sub-mechanism describes the interaction between NO and HNO within the flame. As with the NO₂_Net sub-mechanism, the HNO sub-mechanism is defined by a subset of reactions which does not include any nitrogen fixing reactions. Figure 4.15 shows good agreement between the HNO sub-mechanism contribution to the NO formation as calculated by the developed algorithm (---) and the results from Bohon et al. (—). The HNO sub-mechanism accounts for the negative NO formation values immediately upstream of the reaction zone, at a flame position of 0 cm. At this flame position,

NO is depleted via the reactions in the HNO sub-mechanism, and forms HNO, which in turn reacts to form other intermediate species and ultimately NO in the reaction zone of the flame. The positive contribution to NO formation by the HNO sub-mechanism can be seen by the peak at a flame position of approximately 0.025 cm in Figure 4.15.

4.1.7 Reburn Sub-mechanism

The reburn sub-mechanism is a set of reactions which describe the depletion of NO to the intermediate species N, CN, and HCNO. It effectively describes the manner in which NO formed within the flame can react back to other intermediate species. Its contribution to total NO formation is therefore generally negative, which can be clearly seen in Figure 4.16.

FIGURE 4.16: Comparison of reburn sub-mechanism contribution.

species accumulated within the flame, i.e. the burnout sub-mechanism in the analysis by Bohon et al. As with the prompt and NNX sub-mechanisms, the reburn sub-mechanism leads to the accumulation of species within the flame, for example N, which then reacts later in the flame to form additional NO. The region of positive NO formation by the reburn mechanism in Figure 4.16, where the results from Bohon et al. predict zero NO formation due to the reburn sub-mechanism, is due to the depletion of species accumulated within the flame to form NO.

4.1.8 Deviations between Results & Literature

Where deviations between the sub-mechanism contribution as calculated by Bohon et al. and the contribution using the algorithm developed in this work were identified, the additional flux due to the depletion of accumulated species within the flame was deemed to be the cause. The affected sub-mechanisms were the prompt, NNX, thermal, and reburn sub-mechanisms. To further explain and justify the deviations between the data from the literature and the results of this work, the deviations were summed and plotted against positions in the flame. The deviation between the sub-mechanisms were defined as the contribution to NO formation as calculated by the developed algorithm minus the same contribution as calculated by Bohon et al.:

Figure 4.16 shows the contribution to NO formation by the reburn sub-mechanism as calculated by the developed algorithm (---) and by Bohon et al. (—). The general behaviour of the reburn sub-mechanism is consistent between the two different methods of calculation, i.e. a portion of the NO formed within the reaction zone by the other sub-mechanisms reacts back to form N, CN, and HCNO via the reactions defined in the reburn sub-mechanism. A negative contribution to the total NO formation therefore results. The discrepancy between the calculation by Bohon et al. and the algorithm developed in this work can again be traced back to the flux attributed to the depletion of

$$dev_{sub} = NO_{ROP,sub_Alg.} - NO_{ROP,sub_Lit.} \quad (4.9)$$

where dev_{sub} is the deviation between the calculated contribution using the developed algorithm and the results from Bohon et al. for the sub sub-mechanism. $NO_{ROP,sub_Alg.}$ is the contribution to the total NO formation by sub-mechanism sub as calculated by the algorithm, and $NO_{ROP,sub_Lit.}$ the contribution to the total NO formation by sub-mechanism sub from the literature, i.e. the results from Bohon et al.

The results are shown in Figure 4.17. Figure 4.18 shows the summed total of all deviations (---) from Figure 4.17, plotted against the burnout sub-mechanism as defined by Bohon et al. (—) and seen in Figure 4.3.

FIGURE 4.17: Deviations between sub-mechanism contributions as calculated by Bohon et al. and the developed algorithm.

FIGURE 4.18: Comparison of burnout sub-mechanism contribution and sum of deviations.

The sum total of all deviations between the results from the literature and those obtained by using the algorithm developed shows a good agreement with the burnout sub-mechanism from the work of Bohon et al. The deviation between the two curves, in the range of approximately 0.03 cm to 0.15 cm can be explained by the deviation between the total predicted NO formation as calculated by the algorithm and Bohon et al. (refer to Figures 4.5 and 4.6).

The explanation that the deviations in sub-mechanism contributions to total NO formation is due to the depletion of species accumulated in the flame is therefore justified. Furthermore, the correct distribution of flux from accumulated species within the flame to the prompt, NNX, thermal, and reburn sub-mechanisms is an additional advantage of the developed algorithm over the method of calculation by Bohon et al. The definition of an additional burnout sub-mechanism to group all flux from accumulated species together is therefore also redundant in the developed algorithm and replaced by a more elegant solution and distribution among the defined sub-mechanisms.

4.1.9 Propane Deflagration

The preceding sections detail the validation of the developed algorithm, using reaction path analysis results from the literature [9]. A stoichiometric, freely propagating methane flame was used to confirm the functionality and validity of the algorithm and the reaction path analysis results produced. To further validate the applicability of the developed algorithm to other flame simulations, the results of a reaction path analysis conducted for a stoichiometric, freely propagating propane flame, obtained using the developed algorithm, were compared to results from the literature. Similarly to the validation of the methane flame reaction path analysis, the simulation results from the work by Bohon et al. were used as validation data [9].

The stoichiometric propane flame simulation and resulting initial gas composition was defined by the following global reaction equation, and simulated using CHEMKIN-Pro [1]. The flame simulation and subsequent reaction path analysis was conducted using the chemical kinetic reaction mechanism implemented by Bohon et al. [9].

The initial gas conditions were $T_0 = 373 \text{ K}$, $P_0 = 1 \text{ atm}$, and an inlet velocity of 2.5 times the laminar burning velocity, $u_0 = 2.5S_L$. The reaction path analysis results from Bohon et al. [9] can be seen in Figure 4.19. The corresponding reaction path analysis results calculated using the developed mechanism are shown in Figure 4.20. The reaction path analysis solution, as calculated by the algorithm, converged after five iterations (refer to equation 3.12 in Section 3.4.2). The sub-mechanisms were defined using the same initiation reactions as for the methane flame reaction path analysis, and outlined in Table 4.2.

The overall total NO formation exhibits the same behaviour as that of the methane simulation as described in Section 4.1.2. Prior to the flame front, NO is depleted by the NO₂_Net sub-mechanism as NO forms NO₂. Shortly thereafter, there is a positive net NO formation, as NO₂ reacts back to form NO, again via the reactions specified within the NO₂_Net sub-mechanism. At a flame position of approximately 0 cm, the NO formation begins to decrease rapidly as NO is depleted via the HNO and reburn sub-mechanisms. It is interesting to note that the absolute magnitude of the negative NO formation in this region of the flame (approximately $-0.25 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$) is much larger compared to the stoichiometric methane simulation (approximately $-0.05 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, referring to Figure 4.4). Within the reaction zone of the flame, the NO formation takes on large positive values, mainly via the prompt sub-mechanism, as well as contributions from the NNX, thermal, HNO, and reburn sub-mechanisms. Again, the absolute peak NO formation is much greater for the propane flame than for the methane flame (approximately $0.9 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ compared to $0.45 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Shortly after the reaction zone, the total NO formation decreases rapidly, and is dominated by the contribution from the NNX sub-mechanism. Finally, at greater flame positions, the NO formation reaches a near-constant level, nearly entirely due to the thermal sub-mechanism. As in the results from the freely propagating, stoichiometric methane flame, the undefined sub-mechanism exhibits zero contribution throughout the flame. The defined initiation reactions therefore capture all of the NO production in the flame.

FIGURE 4.19: Reaction path analysis for the stoichiometric combustion of propane as calculated by Bohon et al. [10].

FIGURE 4.20: Reaction path analysis for the stoichiometric combustion of propane as calculated by the developed algorithm.

Regarding the performance of the developed algorithm, it can be seen qualitatively that the relative contributions from each sub-mechanism match those as calculated by Bohon et al (Figure 4.19). Again, the flux attributed to the burnout sub-mechanism is distributed

among the NNX, prompt, and reburn sub-mechanisms in the analysis performed using the developed algorithm. A more detailed explanation regarding the contribution from the burnout sub-mechanism is provided in Section 4.1.8. The prediction of total NO formation as calculated by the algorithm (--- in Figure 4.20) matches the values as calculated by Cantera (o) and exhibits a greater accuracy than the prediction in the results from Bohon et al. (- - - in Figure 4.19).

4.1.10 Burner Stabilised Flat Flames

All of the results presented in the previous subsections detail the reaction path analysis of freely propagating flames. The results show that the developed algorithm can be successfully implemented and applied to such flames. To investigate the applicability of the algorithm to other combustion processes, a reaction path analysis of burner stabilised flat flames was conducted. Flat flames exhibit a much lower NO formation than the freely propagating flames analysed in the preceding sections, due to lower peak temperatures and suppression of the thermal formation mechanism [9]. They do however exhibit rapid NO formation close to the burner surface [9]. The results of the reaction path analysis from the literature for a stoichiometric, burner stabilised, flat methane flame are shown in Figure 4.21. The reaction mechanism and sub-mechanism initiation reactions used for the simulations were the same as for the freely propagating flames, detailed in Table 4.2. The initial gas conditions were: $T_0 = 373$ K, $P_0 = 1$ atm, and an inlet velocity of 0.25 times the laminar burning velocity, $u_0 = 0.25S_L$.

The position plotted is the height above the burner surface. Compared to the stoichiometric, freely propagating methane flame, it is clear that the peak NO formation is an order of magnitude lower for the burner stabilised flat flame. The peak NO formation from Figure 4.21 is approximately $0.06 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ compared to a peak NO formation of approximately $0.45 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the case of the freely propagating flame (Figure 4.4). The contribution from the NO₂_Net sub-mechanism is also more significant for the flat flame. After the initial NO formation due to the NO₂_Net sub-mechanism, the relative contributions to the total NO formation from the individual sub-mechanisms is comparable to those in the freely propagating flame. The prompt sub-mechanism accounts for most of the NO formation, followed by the NNX sub-mechanism at later flame positions. The reburn sub-mechanism has a negative contribution as it is responsible for the depletion of NO. The major noticeable difference is the aforementioned suppression of the thermal sub-mechanism. In Figure 4.21 the contribution from the thermal sub-mechanism is never greater than the NNX contribution throughout the flame, which also explains why the total NO formation tends towards zero at greater flame positions where the thermal sub-mechanism has a significant contribution in the case of the freely propagating flame. Figure 4.22 shows the results from the reaction path analysis for the same burner stabilised flat flame simulation obtained using the algorithm, which converged after five iterations through the flame (refer to Section 3.4.2).

Qualitatively, it is clear that the results from the literature and those obtained by the algorithm show good agreement. The results from the algorithm exhibit an improved total NO formation prediction. In Figure 4.22 the sum of all contributions (---) matches the total NO rate of production (o), compared to the sum of the contributions in the results from the literature (- - -) in Figure 4.21, which underpredict the total NO rate of formation. In the results from the algorithm, the undefined sub-mechanism exhibits no contribution to NO formation at all flame positions, meaning that the defined initiation reactions account for all of the NO production in the flame. As in the case of the freely

propagating flames, the contribution from the burnout sub-mechanism in Figure 4.21 is mostly shared among the prompt, NNX, and reburn sub-mechanisms in Figure 4.22.

FIGURE 4.21: Reaction path analysis for a stoichiometric methane burner stabilised flat flame as calculated by Bohon et al. [10].

FIGURE 4.22: Reaction path analysis for a stoichiometric methane burner stabilised flat flame as calculated by the developed algorithm.

4.1.11 Rich Burner Stabilised Flat Flame

Figures 4.23 and 4.24 show the results of reaction path analyses of a rich, burner stabilised, flat methane flame, as calculated by Bohon et al. and the algorithm respectively.

FIGURE 4.23: Reaction path analysis for a rich methane burner stabilised flat flame as calculated by Bohon et al. [10].

FIGURE 4.24: Reaction path analysis for a rich methane burner stabilised flat flame as calculated by the developed algorithm.

The reaction path analysis solution, as calculated by the algorithm and shown in Figure 4.24, converged after five iterations through the flame (refer to Section 3.4.2). The equivalence ratio for the flame was defined by $\phi = 1.1$. The results show good agreement, with the individual sub-mechanism contributions exhibiting similar behaviour. As in all other previous results, the contribution from the burnout sub-mechanism in Figure 4.23 is distributed predominantly between the prompt and reburn sub-mechanisms. The undefined sub-mechanism again exhibits no contribution to NO formation at all flame positions. The results obtained using the algorithm show small fluctuations in the thermal and reburn contributions at a flame positions of approximate 0.08 cm, likely to be due to a change in flux case. The total NO formation prediction however, matches the NO rate of prediction as calculated by Cantera (\circ) and improves on the total NO formation prediction (- - -) in Figure 4.23. The results shown in Figure 4.24 further validate the developed algorithm for rich flame conditions.

4.2 Detonation

The preceding sections detail the underlying theory and development of an algorithm for conducting reaction path analyses of combustion processes. While being validated against data from the analysis of deflagration processes, and in particular a freely propagating, stoichiometric methane flame, the algorithm developed within the scope of this research was constructed to be applicable to any combustion process. The calculation is dependent only on the molecular composition of the gas to be analysed over a range of spatial positions, e.g. flame positions. To examine the applicability of the developed algorithm to other combustion processes, a reaction path analysis of a detonation wave was conducted.

The detonation wave was simulated using the *Shock and Detonation Toolbox 2018* (SDToolbox), which is an open-source collection of functions and numerical routines developed at the California Institute of Technology (CalTech) for the analysis of detonation processes [87]. The package was used to determine the Zel'dovich, von Neumann, Döring (ZND) structure and resulting post-shock states of the gas being analysed. For an initial simplified simulation, a stoichiometric methane-air detonation wave at standard atmospheric conditions was simulated. The global reaction for the stoichiometric combustion of a methane-air mixture is given by the following chemical equation:

The initial gas conditions were $T_0 = 300 \text{ K}$, $P_0 = 1 \text{ atm}$. The detonation calculation was conducted using the San Diego reaction mechanism, consisting of 321 reactions and 70 species [64]. The resulting calculated ZND and Rayleigh line and Hugoniot curve plots are shown in Figures 4.25 and 4.26. In Figure 4.26, the blue curve (—) represents the Rayleigh line, the red curve (—) the Hugoniot curve with heat release, and the red dashed curve (- - -) the Hugoniot curve without heat release.

The ZND structure of the detonation wave, detailed in Section 2.1.1, is recognisable in Figure 4.25. The pressure, density, and temperature increase nearly instantaneously behind the shock wave to the von Neumann state of 31.1 atm, 21.8 kg m^{-3} , and 1524.0 K. Within the reaction zone, located at a position approximately 26 mm behind the leading shock wave, the temperature increases and the pressure and density decrease as the gas

FIGURE 4.25: ZND Structure for a stoichiometric methane-air detonation wave at initial conditions of $T_0 = 300$ K, $P_0 = 1$ atm.

FIGURE 4.26: Rayleigh line and Hugoniot curve plot for a stoichiometric methane-air detonation wave at initial conditions of $T_0 = 300$ K, $P_0 = 1$ atm.

expands. The state of the gas in the Chapman Jouguet (CJ) state is defined by a pressure, density, and temperature of 16.5 atm, 6.2 kg m^{-3} and 2757.0 K.

The gas composition, temperature, pressure, and velocity at all positions of the detonation shown in Figure 4.25 were written to an output file. The gas composition consists of the mole fractions of all species within the reaction mechanism. The simulation results were then passed to the reaction path analysis algorithm developed as part of this research and detailed in the preceding sections. The defined sub-mechanisms for the reaction path analysis were simplified compared to those defined in the freely propagating methane flame analyses detailed in Section 4.1.2. The initiation reactions defined for the reaction path analysis using the San Diego mechanism can be seen in Table 4.3 below. The reaction numbers refer to the numbers as listed in the full chemical kinetic reaction mechanism which can be found online [64] or in the supplementary material of this work. The resulting reaction path analysis for a stoichiometric methane-air detonation wave can be seen in Figures 4.27 and 4.28.

TABLE 4.3: Sub-mechanism initiation reactions for reaction path analysis of simulated methane detonation wave shown in Figures 4.25 and 4.26.

Sub-mechanism	Name	Reaction #	Reaction
1	Thermal	268	$\text{N}_2 + \text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{N} + \text{NO}$
2	NNX	313	$\text{N}_2 + \text{O} + \text{M} \rightleftharpoons \text{N}_2\text{O} + \text{M}$
		314	$\text{N}_2 + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{H} + \text{N}_2\text{O}$
		316	$\text{N}_2 + \text{HO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{N}_2\text{O} + \text{OH}$
		271	$\text{N}_2 + \text{CH} \rightleftharpoons \text{HCN} + \text{N}$
3	Prompt	293	$\text{N}_2 + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{NH} + \text{NO}$
		297	$\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{NH}_2 + \text{NO}$
		303	$\text{N}_2 + \text{H} \rightleftharpoons \text{N}_2\text{H}$
		304	$\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{N}_2\text{H} + \text{H}$
		306	$\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{N}_2\text{H} + \text{OH}$
4	Undefined		

Initially, in the induction zone of the detonation, there is no total NO formation. The

FIGURE 4.27: Reaction path analysis for a stoichiometric methane-air detonation wave at initial conditions of $T_0 = 300$ K, $P_0 = 1$ atm.

temperature and pressure of the gas are significantly increased compared to the initial conditions but the gas has not ignited and reactions within the gas only progress at relatively low rates. A sharp increase in the total NO formation can be seen in Figures 4.27 and 4.28 at a position of approximately 26 mm, which coincides with the position of the reaction zone as identified in Figure 4.25 and therefore the ignition of the gas. The ignition can also be identified by the significant increase in temperature seen in Figure 4.27. A large amount of heat is released and reactions progress at a very high rate. The total NO formation gradually decreases at positions further from the shock front as the gas state approaches the CJ state.

The scale of total NO formation is also apparent. Comparing the results of the reaction path analysis in Figures 4.27 and 4.28 to those from the freely propagating methane flame used for validation in Section 4.1, the peak NO formation of approximately $5800 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is four magnitudes greater than the peak NO formation of approximately $0.4 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the freely propagating flame. One potential explanation for the large difference in total NO formation is the extreme conditions within the detonation wave. Within the reaction zone of the detonation wave, the pressure is in the range of 15-30 atm, compared to constant atmospheric pressure for the freely propagating flame. The maximum gas temperature of 2757 K within the detonation wave is also much greater than the adiabatic flame temperature of approximately 2226 K within the freely propagating methane flame [94].

The thermal sub-mechanism contributes the most to the total NO formation throughout the entire length of the detonation wave, and has a maximum value of approximately $3200 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at a position of approximately 26.5 mm. Referring to Figure 4.25 it can be seen that the maximum contribution from the thermal sub-mechanism coincides with the the region of the detonation wave where the temperature approaches a maximum. Furthermore, the maximum contributions to the total NO formation by the prompt, NNX, and undefined sub-mechanisms, occurs within the reaction zone of the detonation wave. This is to be expected, as the sub-mechanisms, and the prompt sub-mechanism in particular, are more dependent on the presence of radicals which accumulate at greater concentrations within the reaction zone than outside of it. The respective contributions then

FIGURE 4.28: Reaction path analysis for a stoichiometric methane-air detonation wave at initial conditions of $T_0 = 300$ K, $P_0 = 1$ atm. Zoomed in on reaction zone of the detonation wave.

decrease to a relatively constant value of approximately $500 \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The contribution from the undefined sub-mechanism is similar in magnitude to that from the NNx sub-mechanism, suggesting significant NO formation via an additional reaction path.

The additional NO formation is likely to proceed via the N_2H intermediate species, which is formed by the undefined initiation reactions #303, #304, and #306 in Table 4.3. The greater contribution by the thermal sub-mechanism near the reaction zone compared to the analysis of the deflagration flame is likely to be due to the higher temperatures reached within the detonation.

Furthermore, the results of the reaction path analysis of a stoichiometric methane detonation wave shows the applicability of the developed algorithm to detonation processes. While the analysis of detonation processes conducted in this work, and presented in Figures 4.27 and 4.28, was conducted using the reduced San Diego mechanism, the results show the potential for applying the developed algorithm to detonation waves using more complex chemical kinetic reaction mechanisms and under different conditions.

Chapter 5

Conclusions and Final Comments

In this work, a post-processing algorithm for conducting a reaction path analysis was developed in Python 3.6 and using the open source Cantera library [13]. The algorithm utilises and expands on the element tracing method, developed by Bohon et al. [10], in which the rate of production of a particular species of interest is calculated by tracing an element through all reactions and distributing flux between defined sub-mechanisms. In this manner, the resulting reaction path analysis provides the total rate of production of the target species, along with the contributions to that production by all sub-mechanisms defined. The work by Bohon et al. developed the element tracing method and successfully applied it to conduct NO reaction path analyses for a wide range of freely propagating and burner stabilised flames [9]. While the results provide a good insight into the various relevant sub-mechanisms for the formation of NO in flames, two key limitations exist in the approach applied by Bohon et al. which form the scope of this work. The limitations are:

- In their work, Bohon et al. developed the element tracing method to be applicable only to one chemical kinetic reaction mechanism. Effectively, the selected reaction mechanism was 'hard-coded' into the numerical routines used to conduct the reaction path analyses, which are therefore not applicable to other reaction mechanisms.
- The flux from species which accumulate in the flame was not distributed among the defined sub-mechanisms and instead grouped together in an additional burnout sub-mechanism. While the addition of the burnout sub-mechanisms enables a good prediction of the total rate of production of the target species, the accuracy of the individual contributions from each sub-mechanism is thereby reduced.

In this work, the reaction path analysis algorithm was developed to expand on and improve the element tracing method with respect to the limitations listed above. Firstly, the reaction mechanism is simply an input of the developed algorithm, meaning that any reaction mechanism can be used. As the developed algorithm is a post-processing tool for combustion simulations, the ability to conduct a reaction path analysis for any reaction mechanism greatly increases the applicability of the tool, as it is not limited to simulations conducted with a specific reaction mechanism. Secondly, the element tracing method was developed further to include calculation of the accumulation of species within the flame, represented by the species pool terms. The introduction of the pool terms allowed the accumulation of species to be captured at all flame positions and subsequently the flux from such species to be correctly distributed among the defined sub-mechanisms. The definition of a burnout sub-mechanism, as implemented by Bohon et al. is therefore obsolete and no longer required, and the accuracy of the individual sub-mechanism contributions increased.

The algorithm was validated using Cantera for the total rate of production of the target species, and results from the literature for the individual sub-mechanism contributions. The simulation of a freely propagating, stoichiometric methane flame was chosen for validation of the algorithm. The total target species rate of production, defined as the sum of the contributions from all sub-mechanisms, showed a good agreement with the predicted rate of production from Cantera. Furthermore, the prediction of total rate of target species production was improved on compared to the results from Bohon et al. The prediction of the individual sub-mechanism contributions to the total target species rate of production as calculated by the developed algorithm also showed good agreement with the results from the literature. Qualitatively, the sub-mechanism profiles displayed the same behaviour, i.e. early NO depletion and subsequent formation due to the NO₂_Net sub-mechanism, large NO formation within the flame reaction zone dominated by the prompt sub-mechanism, and NO formation behind the reaction zone dominated by the thermal sub-mechanism. It was found that discrepancies between the results from this work and the literature were most prominent in the prompt, NNX, thermal, and reburn sub-mechanisms. It was postulated that the discrepancies are likely to come from the burnout sub-mechanism implemented in the literature but not required in the analysis conducted by the developed algorithm. The discrepancies between the sub-mechanism contributions, as calculated by the developed algorithm and from the literature, were summed and compared to the contribution by the burnout sub-mechanism from the literature. The total discrepancy showed good agreement with the burnout contribution, supporting the case that the discrepancies between sub-mechanism contributions comes from the difference in approach for analysing the accumulation of species within the flame.

An additional validation was carried out using the reaction path analysis results from a freely propagating, stoichiometric propane flame simulation from the work of Bohon et al. [9]. Again, the individual sub-mechanism contributions showed good agreement with each other, with deviations being attributable to the burnout sub-mechanism implemented in the work by Bohon et al.

The reaction path analyses results for a burner stabilised, flat stoichiometric methane flame and for a burner stabilised, flat rich methane flame ($\phi = 1.1$) obtained from the algorithm were compared to data from the literature. The results showed good agreement, further validating the developed algorithm for other flame types. For the flat flame, the prediction of total NO formation showed a considerable improvement in the developed algorithm to the results from the literature. The deviations in the individual sub-mechanism contributions behaved the same way as in the freely propagating flames, and were due to the burnout sub-mechanism. The thermal and reburn sub-mechanisms displayed small fluctuations in the rich methane flat flame at a flame position of approximately 0.08 cm. The fluctuations are likely to be due to a change in flux case and present a potential for improvement to the algorithm in future work.

Lastly, the developed algorithm was applied to a detonation simulation. The aim of the reaction path analysis was to test the algorithm on a different combustion process other than the freely propagating flames used for validation, and to obtain insight into NO formation within a detonation wave. The detonation wave was simulated using the SDToolbox developed at Caltech, and the complete San Diego chemical kinetic reaction mechanism including nitrogen chemistry. A simplified case, considering the prompt, NNX, and thermal sub-mechanisms was conducted, due to the simplicity of the reaction mechanism applied. The results showed good agreement between the total NO rate of production as calculated by the algorithm, and the total rate of production predicted by Cantera.

The largest contribution to the total NO rate of production came from the thermal sub-mechanism, across all regions of the detonation wave. The prompt sub-mechanism also contributed significantly to the total NO rate of production within the reaction zone of the detonation wave. The increased contribution of the thermal sub-mechanism, compared to the flame simulations considered in the validation cases is likely to be due to the extremely high temperatures within the detonation wave, at which the thermal mechanism of NO formation is known to be dominant. Overall, the reaction path analysis results from the detonation simulation proved the applicability of the developed algorithm to other combustion processes and mechanisms not previously considered.

The developed algorithm provides a fundamental tool for conducting reaction path analyses for a wide range of combustion processes and chemical kinetic reaction mechanisms. Future work should be conducted to improve the computational effort required by the algorithm. With regard to potential applications of the algorithm developed, particularly when using large and complex chemical kinetic reaction mechanisms, a reduced computation effort will greatly increase the usability and effectiveness of the developed algorithm as a tool for fellow researchers. Furthermore, the algorithm can be utilised in future work, to analyse the formation of NO and corresponding sub-mechanism contributions in detonation waves for a wide range of conditions. Additionally, the applicability of the algorithm for the analysis of other processes, such as fuel decomposition, presents an opportunity for further research.

In closing, the algorithm developed within the scope of this thesis provides a tool for analysis of a wide range of combustion processes. With respect to ever more stringent emissions regulations and an increased focus on engineering solutions to reduce pollutant emissions, the analysis of combustion processes and the ability to gain an understanding of the fundamental underlying kinetic mechanisms for pollutant formation will continue to grow in importance. The work completed as part of this thesis and algorithm developed provide a contribution to this area of research.

Appendix A

Initiation Reactions

Sub-mechanism	Reaction #	Reaction
Thermal	1782	$\text{N}_2 + \text{H} \rightleftharpoons \text{NNH}$
NNX	1658	$\text{N}_2 + \text{CO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CO} + \text{N}_2\text{O}$
	1783	$\text{N}_2 + \text{H} \rightleftharpoons \text{NNH}$
	1800	$\text{N}_2 + \text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{N}_2\text{O}$
	1801	$\text{N}_2 + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{N}_2\text{O} + \text{H}$
	1803	$\text{N}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{N}_2\text{O} + \text{O}$
	1804	$\text{N}_2 + \text{HO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{N}_2\text{O} + \text{OH}$
Prompt	1742	$\text{N}_2 + \text{CH} \rightleftharpoons \text{NCN} + \text{H}$
NO ₂ _Net	1716	$2\text{NO} + \text{CO} \rightleftharpoons \text{NCO} + \text{NO}_2$
	1795	$\text{NO}_2 + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{HO}_2 + \text{NO}$
	1796	$\text{NO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{H} + \text{NO}_2$
	1797	$\text{NO} + \text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{O} + \text{NO}_2$
	1653	$\text{NO} + \text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{HCO} + \text{NO}_2$
	1654	$\text{NO} + \text{CO}_2 + \text{H} \rightleftharpoons \text{HCO} + \text{NO}_2$
	1655	$\text{NO} + \text{CO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CO} + \text{NO}_2$
HNO	1636	$\text{NO} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{HNO} + \text{OH}$
	1637	$\text{NO} + \text{H}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{H} + \text{HNO}$
	1650	$\text{HNO} + \text{CO} \rightleftharpoons \text{HCO} + \text{NO}$
	1788	$\text{HNO} \rightleftharpoons \text{H} + \text{NO}$
	1789	$\text{NO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{HNO} + \text{O}$
	1790	$\text{HO}_2 + \text{NO} \rightleftharpoons \text{HNO} + \text{O}_2$
Reburn	1662	$\text{NO} + \text{CH}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{H} + \text{HCNO}$
	1666	$\text{NO} + \text{HCCO} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO} + \text{HCNO}$
	1659	$\text{NO} + \text{C} \rightleftharpoons \text{CN} + \text{O}$
	1660	$\text{NO} + \text{CH} \rightleftharpoons \text{HCN} + \text{O}$
	1661	$\text{NO} + \text{CH}_2(\text{S}) \rightleftharpoons \text{HCN} + \text{OH}$
	1663	$\text{NO} + \text{CH}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{HCN} + \text{OH}$
	1664	$\text{NO} + \text{CH}_3 \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{HCN}$
	1667	$\text{NO} + \text{HCCO} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{HCN}$

Sub-mechanism	Reaction #	Reaction
Undefined	1609	$\text{N}_2 + \text{M} \rightleftharpoons 2\text{N} + \text{M}$
	1618	$\text{N}_2 + \text{H} \rightleftharpoons \text{N} + \text{NH}$
	1619	$\text{N}_2 + 2\text{H} \rightleftharpoons 2\text{NH}$
	1622	$\text{N}_2 + 2\text{H} \rightleftharpoons \text{N} + \text{NH}_2$
	1631	$\text{N}_2 + \text{HNO} \rightleftharpoons \text{NNH} + \text{NO}$
	1632	$\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{H} + \text{NNH}$
	1633	$\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{NNH} + \text{OH}$
	1634	$\text{N}_2 + \text{NH}_3 \rightleftharpoons \text{NH}_2 + \text{NNH}$
	1635	$\text{N}_2 + \text{NH}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NH} + \text{NNH}$
	1657	$\text{N}_2 + \text{NO} \rightleftharpoons \text{N} + \text{N}_2\text{O}$
	1696	$\text{N}_2 + \text{CO} \rightleftharpoons \text{CN} + \text{NO}$
	1702	$\text{N}_2 + \text{C} \rightleftharpoons \text{CN} + \text{N}$
	1705	$\text{N}_2 + \text{NCO} \rightleftharpoons \text{CN} + \text{N}_2\text{O}$
	1715	$\text{N}_2 + \text{CO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NCO} + \text{NO}$
	1720	$\text{N}_2 + \text{CO} + \text{NO} \rightleftharpoons \text{N}_2\text{O} + \text{NCO}$
	1721	$\text{N}_2 + 2\text{CO} \rightleftharpoons 2\text{NCO}$
	1723	$\text{N}_2 + \text{CO} \rightleftharpoons \text{N} + \text{NCO}$
	1741	$\text{N}_2 + \text{CH}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{HCN} + \text{NH}$
	1749	$\text{N}_2 + \text{CH}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{CN} + \text{N}$
	1768	$\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{NH}_2 + \text{NO}$
	1769	$\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{NH}_2 + \text{NO}$
	1779	$\text{N}_2 + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{NH} + \text{NO}$
	1785	$\text{N}_2 + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{NNH} + \text{O}$
	1787	$\text{N}_2 + \text{HO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NNH} + \text{O}_2$

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